

Checklist of the terrestrial gastropods of Brazil

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Abstract. We compiled taxonomic information about terrestrial gastropods in Brazil in an organized and user-friendly checklist that we hope will be useful for researchers and stakeholders alike. We also expect that it will serve as a springboard, garnering more interest and enabling a new wave of studies on this fauna, which has one the highest extinction rates of all animal groups while being essential ecosystem functioning and also includes species of importance to public health and agriculture. We list all species of terrestrial gastropods that occur in the country, with information regarding synonymized names and fossils. We also propose a few nomenclatural acts to address some pending issues of easy resolution. A total of 748 species of terrestrial gastropods are known in Brazil, including 33 exotic species that have been introduced to Brazil. A total of 48 families are present, the majority of which belong to Stylommatophora; only six families represent the Neritimorpha, Caenogastropoda and Systellommatophora. The most speciose families are Bulimulidae, Strophocheilidae, Cyclodontinidae, Streptaxidae, and Simpulopsidae. Changes in nomenclature proposed here are as follows: *Drymaeus obliquus poecilogramma* Ancy, 1901 is now reclassified as *Sanniostracus poecilogramma* (Ancy, 1901) comb. nov.; *Helix uniplicata* Férussac, 1827 as *Clessinia uniplicata* (Férussac, 1827) comb. nov.; *Zonitoides parana* Baker, 1914 as *Miradiscops parana* (Baker, 1914) comb. nov.; “*Helix*” *circumplexa* Deshayes, 1839 as *Systrophiella circumplexa* (Deshayes, 1839) comb. nov.; *Bradybaena giovannalimae* Lima & Cossignani, 2021 as *Streptaxis giovannalimae* (Lima & Cossignani, 2021) comb. nov.

Key words. Cyclophoroidea, exotic species, land snails and slugs, Neritimorpha, Stylommatophora, Systellommatophora

Resumo. Organizamos a informação taxonômica sobre os gastrópodes terrestres brasileiros em um *checklist* de fácil acesso e uso que, esperamos, será útil para pesquisadores e demais partes interessadas. Também esperamos que sirva como um ponto de partida para novos estudos, já que se trata de um dos grupos animais mais ameaçados, porém essenciais para o funcionamento dos ecossistemas; além disso, o grupo também inclui espécies com importância para a saúde pública e agrícola. Listamos aqui todas as espécies de gastrópodes terrestres que ocorrem no Brasil, com informação sobre nomes sinonimizados e fósseis. Propostas de atos nomenclaturais também são feitas para lidar com questões pendentes de simples resolução. Um total de 748 espécies são conhecidas no Brasil, incluindo 33 espécies exóticas introduzidas no país. Um total de 48 famílias estão presentes, a maioria das quais pertence aos Stylommatophora; Neritimorpha, Caenogastropoda e Systellommatophora são, em conjunto, representados por seis famílias. As famílias mais especiosas são Bulimulidae, Strophocheilidae, Cyclodontinidae, Streptaxidae e Simpulopsidae. As mudanças propostas à nomenclatura vigente são: *Drymaeus obliquus poecilogramma* Ancey, 1901 é reclassificado como *Sanniostracus poecilogramma* (Ancey, 1901) comb. nov.; *Helix uniplicata* Férussac, 1827 como *Clessinia uniplicata* (Férussac, 1827) comb. nov.; *Zonitoides parana* Baker, 1914 como *Miradiscops parana* (Baker, 1914) comb. nov.; “*Helix*” *circumplexa* Deshayes, 1839 como *Systrophiella circumplexa* (Deshayes, 1839) comb. nov.; *Bradybaena giovanlimae* Lima & Cossignani, 2021 como *Streptaxis giovannalimae* (Lima & Cossignani, 2021) comb. nov.

Palavras-chave. Cyclophoroidea, caracóis e lesmas terrestres, espécies exóticas, Neritimorpha, Stylommatophora, Systellommatophora.

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INTRODUCTION

It has been estimated that circa 25,000 species of living terrestrial gastropods are known worldwide (Rosenberg 2014), including snails, slugs, and those in between. In Brazil, a megadiverse country for most terrestrial animal taxa (Lewinsohn *et al.* 2005), there is a puzzlingly low number of known terrestrial gastropods: slightly over 700 species (Simone 2006; Salvador 2019; Machado *et al.* 2023).

While there are numerous studies involving the Brazilian terrestrial malacofauna, most, as expected, have a relatively narrow geographic focus or taxonomic scope (e.g., Bequaert 1948 for the family Strophocheilidae, and Thomé 1993 for the Veronicellidae), there have been just three attempts so far to organize and list all the species of terrestrial gastropods in Brazil: the general Mollusca catalogue of Lange de Morretes (1949, with an expansion in 1953), the catalogue of Salgado & Coelho (2003) focused on terrestrial gastropods (but excluding veronicellid slugs), and the handbook of Simone (2006) on all terrestrial and freshwater molluscs (but including some species from neighbouring areas not recorded in Brazil). Nevertheless, all those initiatives were not free of problems and errors, as expected in such complex undertakings. Salvador (2019) explored the state-of-the-art knowledge of the terrestrial gastropod fauna in Brazil but did not provide an update on the country’s species checklist. Thus, a unified consensus is still needed.

Recently, a concerted effort of malacologists in Brazil established a national database of mollusc species via the “Taxonomic Catalogue of the Brazilian Fauna” or “TCBF” (Catálogo Taxonômico da Fauna do Brasil, or CTFB, in Portuguese) (Machado *et al.* 2023). The TCBF is a government-backed bilingual online platform (<http://fauna.jbrj.gov.br/>) where species data can be added and curated in real time, which was a first for South America and an early example in the Global South, where most of the world’s biodiver-

sity resides. The effort that experts in terrestrial gastropods have dedicated to the TCBF Mollusca Group also allowed us to present a much-needed revision of the national checklist of land snails and slugs.

Here we compile all the taxonomic information about terrestrial gastropods in Brazil in an organized and user-friendly manner that we hope will be useful for researchers and stakeholders alike. We also refine and expand upon the information on the TCBF by including missing species, synonymies, and fossils, while also proposing a few nomenclatural acts to address some pending issues.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The species list presented here was built by the team of experts on terrestrial gastropods during work on the TCBF (see Machado *et al.* 2023 for more information). The TCBF uses information from current specialized literature on taxonomy, classification, and geographic distribution, collected by experts in the different taxa of terrestrial gastropods. In essence, the basis of the work on the TCBF was previously published catalogues (Lange de Morretes 1949; 1953; Salgado & Coelho 2003; Simone 2006, 2008; Birkholz *et al.* 2016). The records of species in Brazil were curated from those catalogues and checked against the original publications of the species to be included in the TCBF and the present checklist.

Some additions and corrections were made to those catalogues. Notably, there have been many new species described since 2016. Likewise, species known from other countries have been recently reported for the first time from Brazil as native (Salvador *et al.* 2018b, 2018c, 2020b, 2021a; Silva *et al.* 2019; Salvador & Cavallari 2020; Lima *et al.* 2021) or exotic species (Agudo-Padrón 2017; Teixeira *et al.* 2017; Silva *et al.* 2020). Furthermore, we have included a few additional sources (and Brazilian species) that had been overlooked by those previous studies, namely Férussac (1827), Boettger (1889), and Ihering (1922). Finally, we removed some species which have been listed in Brazil (Salgado & Coelho 2003; Simone 2006) but whose records are instead from other neighbouring countries, normally from the non-Brazilian portion of the Amazon. A few taxa with uncertain occurrences in Brazil were kept here for now, until more evidence comes to light; those taxa are explained in more detail in the Results section.

Furthermore, during work on the TCBF and this checklist, a few nomenclatural issues were found that needed attention. For cases where a simple solution was possible, we propose them here in the Nomenclatural Acts section below.

The complete species checklist is presented in the Results section. The higher classification (family-level and above) of the species checklist follows Bouchet *et al.* (2017), with the additions of modifications based on more recent phylogenetic studies (Calcutt *et al.* 2020; Salvador *et al.* 2020a, 2023b; Salvador 2022). Family-level taxa known to be paraphyletic are retained here for stability and indicated within quotation marks. The checklist provides synonymized names for all native (or presumed so) species recorded from Brazil. For exotic species, we do not provide a full synonymy; instead, we list only those names used by authors who described the exotics as “new species” from South America.

Additionally, the checklist provides information about the status of exotic species: a black diamond symbol (◆) indicates an exotic species that is established in Brazil (or potentially so, as some of them have not been recorded extensively in the literature); two diamonds (◆◆) indicate an exotic species that is present in Brazil only in captivity (e.g., heliciculture). The dagger symbol (†) indicates a species known only from Holocene subfossils, e.g., from archaeological settings such as shell mounds and cave deposits (i.e., species considered extinct in the present); these are listed together with the extant species because they have been found in human-made contexts. The double dagger symbol (‡) indicates a species whose occurrence in Brazil is uncertain.

A genus name within quotation marks indicates cases for which we know that the species does not belong to that genus (as per Salvador *et al.* 2018a, 2023; Roosen & Breure 2024) but a taxonomic revision is lacking.

No geographic occurrence data are provided herein, as that would be beyond the scope of a user-friendly checklist. That information (including references) can be found on the TCBF platform, which is constantly being updated.

Appendix 1 brings a checklist of all known pre-Holocene terrestrial fossil gastropods in Brazil. It was compiled using the information from the catalogue of Salvador *et al.* (2018a) that covered the Cretaceous to the Pliocene, with the addition of further sources on Pleistocene fossils (see Appendix). Appendix 2 provides a comprehensive reference list of the original species-level taxa descriptions of all taxa listed here, including the fossils from Appendix 1.

Most of the authors in the present study are part of the TCBF team of terrestrial gastropod experts. Still, a few new collaborators were also brought on board for this effort (see the Author Contributions section for a taxon-by-taxon list of specialists).

Figure 1. Most speciose families registered in Brazil, ranked by the number of recorded species. Families with less than five recorded species are not included. Different colours indicate the three subclasses.

RESULTS

A total of 748 species of terrestrial gastropods are known in Brazil, including 33 exotic species that have been introduced to the country. A total of 48 families are present, the majority of which belong to Stylommatophora, with other lineages represented by 6 families: Neritimorpha (2 families), Caenogastropoda (3), and Systellommatophora (1). The richest family (i.e., largest number of species) was

Bulimulidae, followed by Strophocheilidae, Cyclodontinidae, Streptaxidae, and Simpulopsidae (Fig. 1). Among the remaining families, 24 have less than five species recorded each (totalling 47 species), including 13 families represented only by exotics; other families can include both exotic/cryptogenic and native species, or native species only (Fig. 2).

The most speciose genera are shown in Figure 3. *Megalobulimus* Miller, 1878 (Strophocheilidae) contain the

Figure 2. Families containing exotic species recorded in Brazil, indicating whether they contain only exotics or a mix of exotic and native species.

largest number of species, followed by *Drymaeus* Albers, 1850 (Bulimulidae), *Helicina* Lamarck, 1799 (Helicinidae, the only non-stylommatophoran among the most speciose taxa), *Solaropsis* Beck, 1837 (Solaropsidae), and *Streptaxis* Gray, 1837 (Streptaxidae). Notably, two families contain three speciose genera each: Bulimulidae (*Auris* Spix, 1827, *Bulimulus* Leach, 1814, and *Drymaeus*) and Simpulopsidae (*Leiostracus* Albers, 1850, *Rhinus* Martens, 1860, and *Simpulopsis* Beck, 1837).

Nomenclatural Acts

During the compilation of this checklist, we came across some problematic taxa that were assigned to a presumably incorrect genus and/or family. For most cases, a full taxonomic investigation will be needed to clarify the situation, but a few cases could fortunately be resolved straightforwardly. We list below the changes in classification proposed here (organized alphabetically by family) and provide a brief explanation for each.

Figure 3. Most speciose genera registered in Brazil, ranked by the number of recorded species. Genera with fewer than 10 recorded species are not included. Different colours indicate subclasses (as in Fig. 1).

Bulimulidae. A recent molecular analysis (Salvador *et al.* 2023b) has moved the species *Leiostracus carnavalescus* Simone & Salvador, 2016 from the family Simpulopsidae to a new genus in the family Bulimulidae, *Sanniostracus* Salvador, Silva & Cavallari, 2023. Meanwhile, a study by Macedo *et al.* (2023a) showed that *Leiostracus obliquus* (Reeve, 1849) was extremely similar to *S. carnavalescus* in the anatomy of its soft parts. However, both studies were published within weeks of one another, and thus could not integrate their results. Thus, here we reclassify *Leiostracus obliquus* as *Sanniostracus obliquus* (Reeve, 1849) comb. nov.

Similarly, the work of Macedo *et al.* (2023a) has brought to light an old variety that has been largely absent from the literature since its initial description, *Drymaeus obliquus poecilogramma* Ancey, 1901. The description of this variety (Ancey 1901) matches the “red morph” of *S. carnavalescus* Simone & Salvador, 2016 (represented by some of the species’ paratypes; Simone & Salvador 2016). The molecular analysis of Salvador *et al.* (2023b) included DNA sequences from both the holotype and a “red morph” paratype, showing that the genetic distance between them was much larger than what is observed between species in other genera from

the same family. That led those authors to postulate that the so-called red morph would represent a distinct species. Thus, herein we propose the reclassification of this morph as *Sanniostracus poecilogramma* (Ancey, 1901) comb. nov.

Cyclodontinidae. The species *Helix uniplicata* Férussac, 1827, only known from its original description based on material from Rio de Janeiro (Férussac 1827), is notably absent from later works on the Brazilian fauna. Herein, based on the conchological features of its type material housed in the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (Paris, France; syntypes MNHN-IM-2000-24634) we reclassify it as *Clessinia uniplicata* (Férussac, 1827) comb. nov. The new classification is due to the narrow, elongated bulimoid shell typical of the Cyclodontinidae, alongside the simple aperture with a columellar plica typical of the representatives of the genus in Brazil (Simone 2006). It is possible that other Brazilian *Clessinia* spp. (e.g., *C. oblita* (Reeve, 1848) and *C. neglecta* (Pfeiffer, 1847)) are synonymous with this species, given their largely similar shell morphology and geographic distribution (Simone 2006), but a more in-depth study is needed to determine this. For now, we retain *Clessinia uniplicata* (Férussac, 1827) comb. nov. as a distinct species.

Moricandia parallela (Pfeiffer, 1857) was considered a distinct species by Simone (2006) but retained tentatively by Breure & Ablett (2012) as a synonym of *Bahiensis occultus* (Reeve, 1849). The type material of both species (NHMUK 1975256 and 1975256, respectively, held at the Museum of Natural History, London, UK) are only marginally similar to one another and thus represent distinct taxa. Simone's (2006) classification in *Moricandia* Pilsbry & Vanatta, 1898 is deemed correct and adopted here. Thus, we reinstate *Moricandia parallela* (Pfeiffer, 1857) as an accepted species distinct from *B. occultus*.

Scolodontidae. *Zonitoides parana* Baker, 1914 has been allocated to the genus *Pseudohyalina* Morse, 1864 (e.g., Simone 2006), which belongs to Gastrododontidae, a family not native to South America (Hausdorf 2001; Schileyko 2003). Further species from Brazil having similar morphology to *Z. parana* have been described in the gastrodontoid genus *Hyalinia* Charpentier, 1837 and later transferred to the native scolodontid genus *Miradiscops* Baker, 1925 (Zilch 1983). These species are *M. fruhstorferi* (Boettger, 1889) and *M. sublenticularis* (Boettger, 1889), which share with *Z. parana* the conchological features typical of *Miradiscops sensu lato* (Ravalo *et al.* 2023), namely the minute size, discoid shell shape, and the sculpture pattern of the shell. As such, given the conchological similarities between *Zonitoides parana* and those species, we reclassify it here as *Miradiscops parana* (Baker, 1914) comb. nov.

Roosen & Breure (2024) removed nearly all species from the genus *Happia* Bourguignat, 1890. A few species that occur in Brazil were transferred to the genera *Systrophie* Baker, 1925, *Austroselenites* Kobelt, 1905, and *Prohappia* Thiele, 1927, but a significant portion of Brazilian species previously allocated in *Happia* were left orphans and were not addressed by Roosen & Breure (2024). As such, until a revision is conducted including said species, they are listed here provisionally as "*Happia*" *iheringi* (Clessin, 1888), "*Happia*" *insularis* (Boettger, 1889), "*Happia*" *microdiscus* Thiele, 1927, "*Happia*" *muelleri* Thiele, 1927, and "*Happia*" *pilsbryi* Gude, 1912.

Similarly, Roosen & Breure (2024) discussed that "*Helix*" *circumplexa* Deshayes, 1839 is not synonymous with *Systrophie* *vitrina* (Wagner, 1827), but they did not present that species in the new combination they strongly suggested. Thus, following their rationale, the species is listed here as *Systrophie* *circumplexa* (Deshayes, 1839) comb. nov.

Streptaxidae. *Bradybaena giovannalimae* Lima & Cossignani, 2021 does not belong to *Bradybaena* Férussac, 1822, an Asian genus. Its homogeneously coloured shell bearing a varix indicates that it belongs instead to the Streptaxidae, and its globose shell shape and elongated aperture places it in the genus *Streptaxis* Gray, 1837, which is quite speciose in Brazil (Simone 2006). Thus, we reclassify the species here as *Streptaxis giovannalimae* (Lima & Cossignani, 2021) comb. nov. Nevertheless, additional investigation is needed to assess if this species is indeed a distinct taxon or synonymous with other common species previously known from the same area, such as the conchologically similar *Streptaxis contusus* (Férussac, 1821).

Strophocheilidae. The species *Megalobulimus sanctipauli* (Ihering & Pilsbry, 1900) was originally described as *Strophocheilus oblongus* var. *sanctepauli* Ihering & Pilsbry in Pilsbry, 1900. The spelling "*sanctipauli*" is thus an unjustified emendation according to Article 33.2.3 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 1999). However, the latter spelling has become more common in the literature than the original form and is currently the prevailing version in use (e.g., Bequaert 1948; Simone 2006; Salvador *et al.* 2021b). Therefore, the spelling "*sanctipauli*" becomes a justified emendation according to Article 33.2.3.1 of the Code (ICZN 1999).

Succineidae. Vidigal *et al.* (2018) synonymized several species of *Omalonyx* d'Orbigny, 1838 based on mathematical models of species delimitation. However, the internal resolution of the *Omalonyx unguis* (d'Orbigny, 1836) complex in their study was low and the clades were largely unsupported,

which should have precluded drawing any taxonomic conclusions from it. Their study would benefit from the addition of another genetic marker that can be used both in the population and at higher taxonomic levels (e.g., Nekola *et al.* 2023) to solve the problematic topology. Furthermore, their study requires better identification of specimens and a comprehensive taxonomic revision considering type specimens, type localities, geographic distributions, and features of the reproductive trait (Arruda 2011). As such, here we retain as valid the species of *Omalonyx* synonymized by Vidigal *et al.* (2018) until further studies are conducted.

Veronicellidae. Recently, Rocha & D'ávila (2019) re-assigned some species from Brazil and Argentina, traditionally classified in the genus *Latipes* Colosi, 1922, to *Angustipes* Colosi, 1922, namely *Latipes absumptus* (Colosi, 1921), *Latipes erinaceus* (Colosi, 1921), *Latipes ribeirensis* (Thiele, 1927), and *Latipes rosillus* (Thiele, 1927). This was done based on traits from genital anatomy (a short and lanceolate penis; Rocha & D'ávila 2019) that are, however, plesiomorphic in Neotropical species (Thomé 1972; Thomé 1993). While we follow the new classification of Rocha & D'ávila (2019) here, we note that a more in-depth phylogenetic study is needed to support the classification of these species.

Furthermore, two of the species listed above, alongside several other veronicellid species from Brazil have vague descriptions and uncertain, juvenile, or missing type material (Thomé 1993). They are considered here *nomina inquirenda*: *Angustipes robustus* (Colosi, 1922), *Angustipes tarsiai* (Coifmann, 1934), *Diplosolenodes attenuatus* (Colosi, 1921), *Latipes absumptus* (Colosi, 1921), *Latipes rosillus* (Thiele, 1927), *Novovaginula langsdorfi* (Férussac, 1821), *Sarasinula kjellerupi* (Semper, 1885), *Vaginulus americanus* (Colosi, 1921), *Vaginulus defiorei* (Coifmann, 1935), *Vaginulus gracilis* (Thiele, 1927), *Vaginulus reclusus* Allemão, 1857, *Vaginulus superbus* Gould, 1852.

Uncertain occurrences. The following species were included in the list below but their occurrences in Brazil are still uncertain: *Clessinia charpentieri* (Pfeiffer, 1850); *Drymaeus schadei* Quintana & Magaldi, 1985 (in open nomenclature in Salvador *et al.* 2023b); *Dryptus moritzianus* (L. Pfeiffer, 1847) (see discussion in Salvador *et al.* 2023a); *Mesembrinus nigrofasciatus* Pfeiffer, 1846 (see discussion in Macedo *et al.* 2023b); *Mesembrinus roseatus* (Reeve, 1850) (see discussion in Macedo *et al.* 2023b); *Odontostomus tenuisculptus* Parodiz, 1963 (see Parodiz 1963 for a discussion on its problematic type locality in Colombia); *Plagiodontes daedaleus* (Deshayes, 1821).

Species Checklist

SUBCLASS NERITIMORPHA

Order Cycloneritida

Superfamily Helicinoidea Férussac, 1822

Family Helicinidae Férussac, 1822

Genus *Alcadia* Gray, 1840

Alcadia iheringi Wagner, 1911

Genus *Helicina* Lamarck, 1799

Helicina angulata Sowerby, 1842

Helicina besckei Pfeiffer, 1849

Helicina biangulata Pfeiffer, 1851

Helicina bicincta Gloyne, 1872

Helicina boettgeri Wagner, 1910

Helicina brasiliensis Gray, 1824 [= *Helicina menkeana* Philippi, 1847; *Helicina oresigera* d'Orbigny, 1835]

Helicina caracolla Moricand, 1836 [= *Helicina moreletiana* Pfeiffer, 1851]

Helicina carinata d'Orbigny, 1835

Helicina chionea Pilsbry, 1949

Helicina concentrica Pfeiffer, 1849

Helicina densestriata Wagner, 1910

Helicina fulva d'Orbigny, 1835

Helicina guajarana Baker, 1914

Helicina haemastoma Moricand, 1838

Helicina iguapensis Pilsbry, 1900

Helicina inaequistriata Pilsbry, 1900

Helicina juruana Ihering, 1905

Helicina laterculus Baker, 1914

Helicina leopoldinae Wagner, 1905

Helicina leptotropis Wagner, 1910

Helicina leucozonalis Ancey, 1892

Helicina lirifera Ancey, 1892

Helicina lundi Pfeiffer, 1858

Helicina marfisae Salvador, Silva & Bichuette, 2023

Helicina oskari Wagner, 1910

Helicina paraensis Pfeiffer, 1859

Helicina rotundata Wagner, 1910

Helicina schereri Baker, 1914

Helicina siolii Haas, 1949

Helicina sordida King & Broderip, 1832

Helicina tilei Pfeiffer, 1847

Helicina variabilis Wagner, 1827 [= *Helicina angulifera* Wagner, 1910]

Helicina wettsteini Wagner, 1905

Family Proserpinidae Gray, 1847

Genus *Proserpina* Sowerby II, 1839

Proserpina derbyi Dall, 1905

SUBCLASS CAENOGASTROPODA

Grade Architaenioglossa

Superfamily Cyclophoroidea Gray, 1847

Family Diplommatinidae Pfeiffer, 1857

Genus *Adelopoma* Doering, 1885*Adelopoma brasiliense* Lange de Morretes, 1954*Adelopoma paraguayana* Parodiz, 1944*Adelopoma paulistanum* Martins & Simone, 2014Genus *Habeastrum* Simone, 2019*Habeastrum omphalium* Simone, 2019*Habeastrum parafusum* Simone, 2019*Habeastrum strangei* Simone, Cavallari & Salvador, 2020

Family Megalomastomatidae Blanford, 1864

Genus *Aperostoma* Troschel, 1847*Aperostoma amazonense* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942*Aperostoma blanchetianum* (Moricand, 1826)*Aperostoma currani* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942*Aperostoma fultoni* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942*Aperostoma inca* (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Cyclostoma colombiensis* Férussac in d'Orbigny, 1835]*Aperostoma merrilli* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942*Aperostoma pulchellum* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942*Aperostoma redfieldi* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942Genus *Cyclopomops* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942*Cyclopomops moricandi* (Pfeiffer, 1852) [= *Cyclostoma disjunctum* Moricand, 1846 (*non* Matheron, 1832)]

Family Neocyclotidae Kobelt & Möllendorff, 1897

Genus *Incidostoma* Bartsch & Morrison, 1942*Incidostoma hedui* (Bartsch & Morrison, 1942)*Incidostoma incomptum* (Sowerby, 1850)*Incidostoma tupy* Simone, 2004Genus *Incerticyclus* Morrison, 1955*Incerticyclus brasiliensis* (Sowerby, 1839) [= *Incerticyclus braziliensis* [sic] Bartsch & Morrison, 1942]Genus *Neocyclotus* Crosse & P. Fischer, 1886*Neocyclotus agassizi* (Bartsch & Morrison, 1942)*Neocyclotus prominulus* (d'Orbigny, 1840)*Neocyclotus stramineus* (Sowerby I, 1843)

SUBCLASS HETEROBRANCHIA

Superorder Eupulmonata

Order Systellommatophora

Superfamily Veronicelloidea Gray, 1840

Family Veronicellidae Gray, 1840

Genus *Angustipes* Colosi, 1922*Angustipes robustus* (Colosi, 1922) *nomen inquirendum**Angustipes tarsiai* (Coifmann, 1934) *nomen inquirendum*Genus *Belocaulus* Hoffmann, 1925*Belocaulus angustipes* (Heynemann, 1885)[= *Vaginula aberrans* Heynemann, 1885]*Belocaulus willibaldoi* Ohlweiler, Mota & Gomes, 2009Genus *Diplosolenodes* Thomé, 1975*Diplosolenodes attenuatus* (Colosi, 1921) *nomen inquirendum*♦ *Diplosolenodes occidentalis* (Guilding, 1824) [= *Veronicella olivacea* Stearns, 1871]Genus *Latipes* Colosi, 1922*Latipes absumptus* (Colosi, 1921) *nomen inquirendum**Latipes erinaceus* (Colosi, 1921)*Latipes ribeirensis* (Thiele, 1927)*Latipes rosillus* (Thiele, 1927) *nomen inquirendum*Genus *Novovaginula* Thiele, 1931*Novovaginula boettgeri* (Semper, 1885)*Novovaginula carinata* (Thiele, 1927)*Novovaginula demorretesi* (Coifmann, 1938)*Novovaginula langsdorfi* (Férussac, 1821) *nomen inquirendum* [= *Vaginula affinis* Simroth, 1914]Genus *Phyllocaulis* Colosi, 1922*Phyllocaulis boraceiensis* Thomé, 1972*Phyllocaulis renschi* Thomé, 1965*Phyllocaulis soleiformis* (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Vaginula galathea* Semper, 1885; *Vaginula kroeyeri* Semper, 1885; *Vaginula multicolor* Semper, 1885; *Vaginula heynemanni* Simroth, 1914; *Vaginula borelliana* Colosi, 1921]*Phyllocaulis tuberculosus* (Martens, 1868) [= *Vaginula abbreviata* Simroth, 1914; *Vaginula albonigra* Simroth, 1914; *Vaginula grisea* Simroth, 1914; *Vaginula palleans* Simroth, 1914]*Phyllocaulis variegatus* (Semper, 1885) [= *Vaginula doellojuradoi* Gambetta, 1923; *Veronicella pardalis* Thiele, 1927; *Veronicella brasiliensis* Thiele, 1927]Genus *Potamojanuarius* Thomé, 1975*Potamojanuarius fuscus* (Heynemann, 1885)*Potamojanuarius lamellatus* (Semper, 1885)Genus *Sarasinula* Grimpe & Hoffmann, 1924*Sarasinula kjellerupi* (Semper, 1885) *nomen inquirendum**Sarasinula linguaeformis* (Semper, 1885) [= *Vaginula calcifera* Simroth, 1914; *Sarasinula arnaldoi* Thomé, 1967]*Sarasinula marginata* (Semper, 1885) [= *Vaginula antillarum* Baker, 1926]

Sarasinula plebeia (Fisher, 1868) [= *Vaginula behni* Semper, 1885; *Vaginula dubia* Semper, 1885; *Sarasinula lemei* Thomé, 1967]

Genus *Simrothula* Thomé, 1975

Simrothula paraensis Gomes, Picanco, Mendes & Thomé, 2006

Genus *Vaginulus* Férussac, 1821

Vaginulus americanus (Colosi, 1921) *nomen inquirendum*

Vaginulus defiorei (Coifmann, 1935) *nomen inquirendum*

Vaginulus gracilis (Thiele, 1927) *nomen inquirendum*

Vaginulus reclusus Allemão, 1857 *nomen inquirendum*

Vaginulus superbus Gould, 1852 *nomen inquirendum*

Vaginulus taunaisii Férussac, 1821

Genus *Veronicella* Blainville, 1817

Veronicella fuscescens (Thiele, 1927)

Order Stylommatophora

Suborder Achatinina

Superfamily Achatinoidea Swainson, 1840

Family Achatinidae Swainson, 1840

Subfamily Achatininae Swainson, 1840

Genus *Achatina* Lamarck, 1799

◆ *Achatina fulica* (Bowdich, 1822)

◆◆ *Achatina achatina monochromatica* Pilsbry, 1904

Subfamily Subulininae Fischer & Crosse, 1877

Genus *Allopeas* Baker, 1935

◆ *Allopeas gracile* (Hutton, 1834)

Allopeas micra (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Bulimus octonoides* Adams, 1845; *Achatina lucida* Poey, 1852; *Bulimus contractus* Poey, 1853; *Bulimus tryonianus* Tate, 1870; *Stenogyra (Opeas) dresseli* Miller, 1879; *Opeas tryonianum subovale* von Martens, 1898]

Genus *Beckianum* Baker, 1961

Beckianum beckianum (Pfeiffer, 1846) [= *Bulimus caraccasensis* Reeve, 1849]

Beckianum regulare (Pfeiffer, 1852)

Genus *Dysopeas* Baker, 1927

Dysopeas muibum Marcus & Marcus, 1968

Genus *Lamellaxis* Strebel & Pfeffer, 1882

Lamellaxis clavulinus (Potiez & Michaud, 1838)

Lamellaxis mizius Marcus & Marcus, 1968

Genus *Lavajatus* Simone, 2018

Lavajatus moroi Simone, 2018

Genus *Leptinaria* Beck, 1837

Leptinaria anomala (Pfeiffer, 1846)

Leptinaria bequaerti Pilsbry, 1926

Leptinaria charlottei Baker, 1922 [= *Leptinaria imperforata* Baker, 1914]

Leptinaria mamoreensis Baker, 1926 [= *Leptinaria perforata* Baker, 1914]

Leptinaria monodon (Adams, 1849) [= *Leptinaria opalescens* Shuttleworth, 1854; *Leptinaria stylydon* Shuttleworth, 1854]

Leptinaria orysa (Bruguière, 1789) *nomen inquirendum*

Leptinaria parana Pilsbry, 1926

Leptinaria ritchei Pilsbry, 1907

Leptinaria unilamellata (d'Orbigny, 1838) [= *Achatina lamellata* Potiez & Michaud, 1838; *Achatina concentrica* Reeve, 1849; *Leptinaria antillarum* Shuttleworth, 1854; *Leptinaria valenzuela* Jousseaume, 1887]

Genus *Subulina* Beck, 1837

◆ *Subulina octona* (Bruguière, 1789)

Subulina parana Pilsbry, 1906

Genus *Vegrandinia* Salvador, Cunha & Simone, 2013

Vegrandinia trinidadensis (Breure & Coelho, 1976)

Subfamily Opeatinae Thiele, 1931

Genus *Opeas* Albers, 1850

◆ *Opeas hannense* (Rang, 1831) [= *Helix goodallii* Miller, 1822]

◆ *Opeas opella* Pilsbry & Vanatta, 1905

Subfamily Rumininae Wenz, 1923

Genus *Rumina* Risso, 1826

◆ *Rumina decollata* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Subfamily Stenogyrinae Fischer & Crosse, 1877

Genus *Neobeliscus* Pilsbry, 1896

Neobeliscus calcareus (Born, 1780)

Genus *Obeliscus* H. Beck, 1837

Obeliscus agassizi Pilsbry, 1906

Obeliscus boitata Simone & Salvador, 2016

Obeliscus carphodes (Pfeiffer, 1855)

Obeliscus columella (Philippi, 1844)

Obeliscus obeliscus (Moricand, 1834)

Obeliscus pattalus Pilsbry, 1906

Obeliscus planospirus (Pfeiffer, 1855)

Obeliscus subuliformis (Moricand, 1836)

Obeliscus sylvaticus (Spix, 1827)

Genus *Rectobelus* Baker, 1927

† *Rectobelus levogyrus* Simone & D'ávila, 2019

Genus *Stenogyra* Shuttleworth, 1854

Stenogyra amazonica (Pilsbry, 1906)

Stenogyra bacillus (Pfeiffer, 1862)

Stenogyra octogyra (Pfeiffer, 1856)

Genus *Synapterpes* Pilsbry, 1896*Synapterpes coronatus* (Pfeiffer, 1846)*Synapterpes hanleyi* (Pfeiffer, 1846)**Family Ferussaciidae Bourguignat, 1883****Genus *Geostilbia* Crosse, 1867***Geostilbia blandiana* Crosse, 1886*Geostilbia gundlachi* (Pfeiffer, 1850)**Genus *Karolus* de Folin, 1870***Karolus consobrinus* (d'Orbigny, 1841) [= *Achatina pygmaea* Pfeiffer, 1847; *Glandina minutissima* Guppy, 1868]**Superfamily Streptaxoidea Gray, 1860****Family Streptaxidae Gray, 1860****Subfamily Enneinae Bourguignat, 1883****Genus *Gulella* Pfeiffer, 1856**♦ *Gulella bicolor* (Hutton, 1834)**Subfamily Streptaxinae Gray, 1860****Genus *Hypselartemon* Wenz, 1947***Hypselartemon alveus* (Dunker, 1845) [= ?*Helix contermina* Reeve, 1854]*Hypselartemon contusus* (Férussac, 1827)*Hypselartemon deshaysianus* (Crosse, 1863)*Hypselartemon paivanus* (Pfeiffer, 1867)**Genus *Martinella* Jousseau, 1887***Martinella prisca* Thiele, 1927**Genus *Rectartemon* Baker, 1925***Rectartemon candidus* (Spix, 1827) [= *Helix perspectiva* Spix, 1827; *Solarium vitreum* Spix, 1827; *Helix candida striata* Moricand, 1836; *Helix candida laevis* Moricand, 1836; *Helix spixiana* Pfeiffer, 1841]*Rectartemon costulosus* (Pfeiffer, 1853)*Rectartemon depressus* (Hyneman, 1868) [= *Helix belcheri* Pfeiffer, 1846; *Streptaxis apertus* Martens, 1868; *Streptaxis apertus depressus* Martens 1868; *Streptaxis apertus subglobosus* Martens 1868]*Rectartemon iguapensis* (Pilsbry, 1930)*Rectartemon iheringi* (Thiele, 1927) [= *Streptaxis jheringi* Thiele, 1927]*Rectartemon muelleri* (Thiele, 1927)*Rectartemon piquetensis* (Pilsbry, 1930)*Rectartemon regius* (Löbbecke, 1881)*Rectartemon wagneri* (Pfeiffer, 1841) [= *Helix cofreana* Moricand, 1841]**Genus *Sairostoma* F. Haas, 1938***Sairostoma perplexum* Haas, 1938**Genus *Streptartemon* Kobelt, 1905***Streptartemon abunaensis* (Baker, 1914)*Streptartemon comboides* (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Helix chiquitensis* Moricand, 1836; *Helix comboides laevigata* d'Orbigny, 1837]*Streptartemon cookeanus* (Baker, 1914)*Streptartemon cryptodon* (Moricand, 1851)*Streptartemon cumingianus* (Pfeiffer, 1850)*Streptartemon decipiens* (Crosse, 1865)*Streptartemon deformis* (Férussac, 1821) [= *Streptaxis glabra* Pfeiffer, 1850; *Streptaxis normalis* Jousseau, 1889; *Streptaxis* (*Odontartemon*) *glaber aroae* Baker, 1925]*Streptartemon dejectus* (Moricand, 1836) [= *Helix comboides brasiliensis* Moricand, 1836; *Helix dejecta* Petit de la Saussaye, 1842; *Helix comboides edentula* Moricand, 1846; *Helix comboides elata* Moricand, 1846]*Streptartemon deplanchei* (Drouët, 1859) [= *Streptaxis* (*Streptartemon*) *deplanchei martiniana* Venmans, 1963]*Streptartemon extraneus* (Haas, 1955)*Streptartemon molaris* Simone & Casati, 2013*Streptartemon quixadaensis* (Baker, 1914)*Streptartemon streptodon* (Moricand, 1851)*Streptartemon waukeen* Salvador & Cunha, 2020**Genus *Streptaxis* Gray, 1837***Streptaxis candei* Petit de la Saussaye, 1842 [= *Streptaxis candeana* Pfeiffer, 1842]*Streptaxis capillosus* Pilsbry, 1897*Streptaxis contusus* (Férussac, 1821) [= *Helix* (*Helicogena*) *contundata* Férussac, 1821]*Streptaxis crossei* (Pfeiffer, 1867)*Streptaxis cypsele* (Pfeiffer, 1849)*Streptaxis decussatus* Pilsbry, 1897*Streptaxis dunkeri* (Pfeiffer, 1845) [= *Streptaxis funcki* Pfeiffer, 1848; *Streptaxis dunkeri clausa* Löbbecke, 1881]*Streptaxis giovannalimae* (Lima & Cossignani, 2021) comb. nov.*Streptaxis helios* Pilsbry, 1897*Streptaxis hylephilus* (d'Orbigny, 1835)*Streptaxis iheringi* (Pilsbry, 1930)*Streptaxis intermedius* (Albers, 1857)*Streptaxis leirae* Salvador, 2018*Streptaxis luetzelburgi* Weber, 1925*Streptaxis megahelix* Salvador, 2018*Streptaxis pfeifferi* (Pilsbry, 1930) [= *Helix spixiana* Pfeiffer, 1848 (*non* Pfeiffer, 1841)]*Streptaxis pilsbryi* (Solem, 1956)*Streptaxis politus* Fulton, 1899

Streptaxis rollandi (Bernardi, 1857)
Streptaxis saopaulensis Pilsbry, 1930
Streptaxis subregularis (Pfeiffer, 1846)
Streptaxis tumulus Pilsbry, 1897
Streptaxis uberiformis Pfeiffer, 1848

Suborder Scolodontina

Superfamily Scolodontoidea Baker, 1925

Family Scolodontidae Baker, 1925

Unassigned subfamily

Genus Polygyratia Gray, 1847

Polygyratia polygyrata (Born, 1778) [= *Helix elongata*
 Röding, 1798; *Polygyratia charybdis* Mörch, 1852]

Genus Ridleyconcha Christensen, 2020

Ridleyconcha quinquelirata (Smith, 1890)

Subfamily Scolodontinae Baker, 1925

Genus Austroselenites Kobelt, 1905

Austroselenites euspira (Reeve, 1854)

Genus Drepanostomella Bourguignat, 1890

Drepanostomella ammoniformis (d'Orbigny, 1835)

Genus Happia Bourguignat, 1890

Happia ammonoceras (Reeve, 1854)

"*Happia*" *iheringi* (Clessin, 1888)

"*Happia*" *insularis* (Boettger, 1889)

"*Happia*" *microdiscus* Thiele, 1927

"*Happia*" *muelleri* Thiele, 1927

"*Happia*" *pilsbryi* Gude, 1912 [= *Happia iheringi*
 Pilsbry, 1900]

Genus Prohappia Thiele, 1927

Prohappia besckei (Dunker, 1847)

Genus Systrophiella Baker, 1925

Systrophiella circumplexa (Deshayes, 1839) comb. nov.

Systrophiella pygmaea (Spix, 1827) [= *Helix nana*
 Wagner, 1827]

Systrophiella snethlagei (Baker, 1914)

Systrophiella vitrina (Wagner, 1827) [= *Solarium*
imperforatum Spix, 1827; *Helix valvaeformis*
 "Nyst", 1853 *nomen nudum*; *Streptaxis (Happia)*
tumescens Suter, 1900; *Happia vitrina muelleri*
 Thiele, 1927]

Genus Scolodonta Doering, 1875

Scolodonta amazonica (Dohrn, 1882)

Scolodonta bounobaena (d'Orbigny, 1835)

Scolodonta interrupta (Suter, 1900)

Scolodonta mutata (Gould, 1846) [*non Helix mutata*
 Lamarck, 1822]

Scolodonta nitidula (Dohrn, 1882)

Scolodonta spirorbis (Deshayes, 1850)

Genus Systrophia Pfeiffer, 1855

Systrophia alcidiana Ancey, 1892

Systrophia cheilostropha (d'Orbigny, 1835)

Systrophia derbyi (Ihering, 1912)

Systrophia eatoni Baker, 1914

Systrophia exigua Thiele, 1927

Systrophia gionensis (Lange de Morretes, 1941)

Systrophia helicocloides (d'Orbigny, 1835)

Systrophia heligmoida (d'Orbigny, 1835)

Systrophia janeirensis (Pfeiffer, 1852)

Systrophia jekylli (Baker, 1914)

Systrophia lundii (Mörch, 1871)

Systrophia siolii Haas, 1955

Subfamily Tamayoinae Tillier, 1980

Genus Guestieria Crosse, 1872

Guestieria shuttleworthi (Pfeiffer, 1851)

Genus Happiella Baker, 1925

Happiella grata (Thiele, 1927)

Genus Miradiscops Baker, 1925

Miradiscops brasiliensis (Thiele, 1927)

Miradiscops fruhstorferi (Boettger, 1889)

Miradiscops parana (Baker, 1914) comb. nov.

Miradiscops sublenticularis (Boettger, 1889)

Genus Tamayoa Baker, 1925

Tamayoa banghaasi (Thiele, 1927)

Suborder Helicina

Helicina incertae sedis

Family Helicodiscidae Baker, 1927

Genus Helicodiscus Morse, 1864

◆ *Helicodiscus parallelus* (Say, 1821) [= *Helicodiscus*
theresa Thiele, 1927]

Superfamily Punctoidea Morse, 1864

Family "Charopidae" Hutton, 1884

Genus Amphidoxa Albers, 1850

Amphidoxa flammulata Ihering, 1922

Amphidoxa inexpectata Ihering, 1922

Genus Radiodiscus Pilsbry, 1906

Radiodiscus amoenus (Thiele, 1927) [= *Radioconus*
crenulatus Hylton Scott, 1963]

Radiodiscus compactus (Suter, 1900) [= *Endodonta*
jheringi Thiele, 1927; *Radiodiscus katiae* Hylton

Scott, 1948; *Radiodiscus tenellus* Hylton Scott,

1958; *Radiodiscus wygodzinskyi* Weyrauch, 1965;

Radiodiscus bolachaensis Fonseca & Thomé, 1994]

Radiodiscus costellifer Hylton-Scott, 1957

Radiodiscus cuprinus Fonseca & Thomé, 2000

Radiodiscus goeldii (Thiele, 1927)

Radiodiscus iheringi (Ancey, 1899)
Radiodiscus promatensis Miquel, Ramírez & Thomé,
 2004
Radiodiscus thomei Weyrauch, 1965
Radiodiscus ubtaoi Salvador, Charles, Simone &
 Maestrati, 2018
Radiodiscus vazi Fonseca & Thomé, 1995

Genus Retidiscus Fonseca & Thomé, 1995

Retidiscus reticulatus Fonseca & Thomé, 1995

Genus Rotadiscus Pilsbry, 1926

Rotadiscus amancaezensis (Hidalgo, 1869) [= *Pyramidula* (*Gonyodiscus*) *schuppi* Suter, 1900; *Endodonta discoidea* Thiele, 1927; *Endodonta janeirensis* Thiele, 1927; *Stephanoda jujuyensis* Hylton Scott, 1948]
Rotadiscus liciae (Vaz, 1991)

Family Cystopeltidae Cockerell, 1891**Genus Lilloiconcha Weyrauch, 1965**

Lilloiconcha clara (Thiele, 1927)
Lilloiconcha gordurasensis (Thiele, 1927) [= *Austrodiscus golbachii* Hylton Scott, 1963]
Lilloiconcha pleurophora (Moricand, 1846)
Lilloiconcha superba (Thiele, 1927)
Lilloiconcha tucumana (Hylton Scott, 1963)
Lilloiconcha zulmae (Miquel, Ramírez & Thomé, 2004)

Genus Zilchogyra Weyrauch, 1965

Zilchogyra deliciosa (Thiele, 1927)
Zilchogyra paulistana (Hylton Scott, 1973)

Family Punctidae Morse, 1864**Genus Paralaoma Iredale, 1913**

◆ *Paralaoma servilis* (Shuttleworth, 1852) [= *Radiodiscus pilsbryi* Hylton Scott, 1957; *Radiodiscus misionensis* Hylton Scott, 1957; *Zilchogyra cleliae* Weyrauch, 1965]

Superfamily Discoidea Thiele, 1931 (1866)**Family Discidae Thiele, 1931 (1866)****Genus Anguispira Morse, 1864**

◆ *Anguispira alternata* (Say, 1817)

Superfamily Urocoptoidea Pilsbry, 1898 (1868)**Family Urocoptidae Pilsbry, 1898 (1868)****Genus Habeas Simone, 2013**

Habeas centraris Simone, 2022
Habeas claudus Simone, 2022
Habeas corpus Simone, 2013
Habeas data Simone, 2013

Habeas lapensis Simone, 2022
Habeas lekolus Simone, 2022
Habeas peruassus Simone, 2022
Habeas priscus Simone, 2013

Superfamily Succineoidea Beck, 1837**Family Succineidae Beck, 1837****Genus Omalonyx d'Orbigny, 1837**

Omalonyx brasiliensis (Simroth, 1896)
Omalonyx convexus (Martens, 1868) [= *Omalonyx patera* Döring, 1873; *Homalonyx gallardoi* Hylton Scott & Lapuente, 1968; *Homalonyx weyrauchi* Hylton Scott, 1971]
Omalonyx geayi Tillier, 1980
Omalonyx matheroni (Potiez & Michaud, 1838) [= *Testacella guadeloupensis* Lesson, 1838; *Amphibulima* (*Omalonyx*) *felina* Guppy, 1872]
Omalonyx pattersonae Tillier, 1981
Omalonyx unguis (d'Orbigny, 1836)

Genus Oxyloma Westerlund, 1885

Oxyloma beckeri Lanzieri, 1966

Genus Succinea Draparnaud, 1801

Succinea burmeisteri Doering, 1873
Succinea lopesi Lanzieri, 1966
Succinea manaosensis Pilsbry, 1926
Succinea meridionalis d'Orbigny, 1837 [= *Succinea meridionalis cornea* Doering, 1873]

Superfamily "Rhytidoidea" Pilsbry, 1893 sensu lato**Family Odontostomidae Pilsbry & Vanatta, 1898****Genus Anthinus Albers, 1850**

Anthinus albolabiatus (Jaekel, 1927)
Anthinus myersii (Sowerby, 1838)
Anthinus morenus Simone, 2022
Anthinus multicolor (Rang, 1831)
Anthinus savanicus Simone, 2022
Anthinus synchronus Simone, 2022
Anthinus turnix (Gould, 1846)
Anthinus vailanti Simone, 2022

Genus Gonyostomus Beck, 1837

Gonyostomus egregius (Pfeiffer, 1845) [= *Bulimus hybridus* Gould, 1846]
Gonyostomus elinae Simone, 2016
Gonyostomus gonyostomus (Férussac, 1821) [= *Limnaeus papyraceus* Spix, 1827]
Gonyostomus insularis Leme, 1974

Genus Odontostomus Beck, 1837

Odontostomus dautzenbergianus Pilsbry, 1898
Odontostomus degeneratus Pilsbry, 1898

Odontostomus fasciatus (Pfeiffer, 1869)
Odontostomus gargantua (Férussac, 1821) [= *Macro-*
dontes sowerbeyii Swainson, 1840; *Macrodontes*
joergensenianus Holmberg, 1912; *Macrodontes*
thielei Pilsbry, 1930]
Odontostomus grayanus (Pfeiffer, 1845)
Odontostomus koenigswaldi (Thiele, 1906)
Odontostomus odontostoma (Sowerby, 1824)
Odontostomus paulista Pilsbry & Ihering, 1898
Odontostomus simplex (Thiele, 1906)
‡ *Odontostomus tenuisculptus* Parodiz, 1963

Family Strophocheilidae Pilsbry, 1902

Subfamily Megalobuliminae Leme, 1973

Genus *Megalobulimus* Miller, 1878

Megalobulimus abbreviatus (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus albescens (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus albus (Bland & Binney, 1872) [= *Strophocheilus oblongus tobagoensis* Pilsbry, 1895; *Bulimus oblongus albolabiata* Smith, 1895]
Megalobulimus amandus Simone, 2012
Megalobulimus arapotiensis Lange de Morretes, 1952
Megalobulimus auritus (Sowerby, 1838)
Megalobulimus bertae (Lange de Morretes, 1952)
Megalobulimus bronni (Pfeiffer, 1847)
Megalobulimus capillaceus (Pfeiffer, 1855)
Megalobulimus cardosoi (Lange de Morretes, 1952)
Megalobulimus chionostomus (Mörch, 1852)
Megalobulimus conicus (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus crassus (Albers, 1850)
† *Megalobulimus diluvianus* Fontenelle & Salvador, 2023
Megalobulimus dryades Fontenelle Simone & Cavallari, 2021
Megalobulimus elongatus (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus elsae Falconieri, 1994
Megalobulimus foreli (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus fragilior (Ihering, 1901)
Megalobulimus garbeanus (Leme, 1964)
Megalobulimus globosus (Martens, 1876) [= *Strophocheilus filipponei* Ihering, 1928]
Megalobulimus granulosus (Rang, 1831) [= *Bulimus haemastomus santaecatharinae* Lesson, 1831]
Megalobulimus gummatum (Hidalgo, 1870)
Megalobulimus haemastomus (Scopoli, 1786)
Megalobulimus hector (Pfeiffer, 1857)
Megalobulimus intercedens (Martens, 1876)
Megalobulimus intertextus (Pilsbry, 1895) [= *Psiloiculus bereniceae* Lange de Morretes, 1952]

† *Megalobulimus jaguarunensis* Fontenelle, Cavallari & Simone, 2014
Megalobulimus klappenbachi Leme, 1964
Megalobulimus leonardosi (Lange de Morretes, 1952)
Megalobulimus lopesi Leme, 1989
Megalobulimus martensianus (Pilsbry, 1902) [= *Bulimus grandis* Martens, 1885]
Megalobulimus mauricius Falconieri, 1995
Megalobulimus maximus (Sowerby, 1825) [= *Helix* (*Cochlogena*) *kremnoica* d'Orbigny, 1835]
Megalobulimus mogianensis Simone & Leme, 1998
Megalobulimus musculus (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus nodai Lange de Morretes, 1952
Megalobulimus oblongus (Müller, 1774) [= *Helix ovipara* Solander, 1786; *Bulla occidua* Shaw, 1797; *Bulimus hemastomus* de Roissy, 1805; *Bulimus roseus* Montfort, 1810; *Helix ovalis* Wood, 1818; *Ampullaria rosea* Spix, 1827; *Helix semilineata* Menke, 1828; *Bulimus vaporeus* Mousson, 1870; *Strophocheilus* (*Borus*) *capillaceus* Weber, 1925]
Megalobulimus oliveirai (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus oosomus (Pilsbry, 1895)
Megalobulimus ovatus (Müller, 1774) [= *Helix ovipara* Solander, 1786; *Helix ovalis* Gmelin, 1790]
Megalobulimus parafragilior Leme & Indrusiak, 1990
Megalobulimus paranaguensis (Pilsbry & Ihering, 1900)
Megalobulimus pergranulatus (Pilsbry, 1901)
Megalobulimus pintoii Lange de Morretes, 1952
Megalobulimus popelairianus (Nyst, 1845) [= *Bulimus popelairianus connectens* Martens, 1876; *Bulimus popelairianus dohrnianus* Martens, 1876; *Bulimus popelairianus thammianus* Martens, 1876]
Megalobulimus proclivis (Martens, 1888) [= *Bulimus iheringi* Clessin, 1888]
Megalobulimus pygmaeus (Bequaert, 1948)
Megalobulimus riopretensis Simone & Leme, 1998
Megalobulimus rolandianus Lange de Morretes, 1952
Megalobulimus sanctipauli (Ihering & Pilsbry, 1900)
Megalobulimus terrestris (Spix, 1827) [= *Bulimus corrugatus* Spix, 1827; *Helix* (*Cochlogena*) *cantagallanus* Rang, 1831; *Bulimus proximus* Sowerby, 1838; *Bulimus* (*Borus*) *accelerans* Martens, 1867]
Megalobulimus valenciennesii (Pfeiffer, 1842)
Megalobulimus versatilis (Fulton, 1905)
Megalobulimus vestitus (Pilsbry, 1926)
Megalobulimus wohlersi Lange de Morretes, 1952
Megalobulimus yporanganus (Ihering & Pilsbry, 1901) [= *Strophocheilus ovatus iguapensis* Maury, 1935; *Megalobulimus toriis* Lange de Morretes, 1937]

Subfamily Strophocheilinae Pilsbry, 1902**Genus *Austroborus* Parodiz, 1949***Austroborus lutescens* (King & Broderip, 1832)**Genus *Catracca* Simone, 2022***Catracca uhlei* Simone, 2022**Genus *Mirinaba* Lange de Morretes, 1955***Mirinaba antoninensis* (Lange de Morretes, 1952)*Mirinaba cadeadensis* (Lange de Morretes, 1952)*Mirinaba curitybana* (Lange de Morretes, 1952)*Mirinaba cuspidens* (Lange de Morretes, 1952)*Mirinaba erythrosoma* (Pilsbry, 1895)*Mirinaba fusoides* (Bequaert, 1948)*Mirinaba jaussaudi* (Lange de Morretes, 1937)*Mirinaba planidens* (Michelin, 1831)*Mirinaba porphyrostoma* (Clench & Archer, 1930)*Mirinaba unidentata* (Sowerby, 1825)**Genus *Speironepion* Bequaert, 1948***Speironepion iguapensis* (Pilsbry, 1901)*Speironepion kronei* (Ihering, 1901)*Speironepion milleri* (Sowerby, 1833)*Speironepion pilsbryi* (Ihering, 1900)**Genus *Strophocheilus* Spix, 1827***Strophocheilus calus* Pilsbry, 1901*Strophocheilus debilis* Bequaert, 1948*Strophocheilus miersi* Da Costa, 1904*Strophocheilus pudicus* (Müller, 1773) [= *Helix erubescens* Solander, 1786; *Bulimus virgineus* Bruguière, 1789; *Voluta aurisvirgins* Dillwyn, 1817; *Partula australis* Bowdich, 1822; *Bulimus almeida* Spix, 1827; *Bulinus perplexus* Sowerby, 1838; *Strophocheilus pudicus roseolabris* Bequaert, 1948]**Superfamily Orthalicoidea Martens, 1860****Family Amphibulimidae Fischer, 1873****Genus *Dryptus* Martens, 1860**‡ *Dryptus moritzianus* (Pfeiffer, 1847) [= *Strophocheilus moritzianus wilsoni* Pilsbry, 1895]**Genus *Plekocheilus* Guilding, 1827***Plekocheilus aurissciuri* Guppy, 1866 [= *Auris aurissciuri lutea* Clapp, 1927]*Plekocheilus distortus* (Bruguière, 1789) [= *Auris distorta bisuturalis* Pilsbry, 1896; *Auris distorta gracilis* Pilsbry, 1896; *Auris distorta panamensis* Pilsbry, 1910; *Auris distorta sublaevis* Pilsbry, 1896; *Plekocheilus guaiensis* Jousseume, 1889]*Plekocheilus floccosus* (Spix, 1827) [= *Bulimus lacrimosus* Heimburg, 1884; *Bulimus pintandinus* d'Orbigny, 1837; *Helix onca* d'Orbigny, 1835; *Helix pentadina* d'Orbigny, 1835]*Plekocheilus fusitorsus* (Oberwimmer, 1931)*Plekocheilus gibbonius* (Lea, 1836)*Plekocheilus rhodocheilus* (Reeve, 1849)*Plekocheilus lacerta* (Pfeiffer, 1855)*Plekocheilus piperitus* (Sowerby, 1833)**Family Bothriembryontidae Iredale, 1937****Subfamily "Prestonellinae" van Bruggen, Herbert & Breure, 2016****Genus *Alterorhinus* Salvador, Silva & Cavallari, 2023***Alterorhinus constrictus* (Pfeiffer, 1841) [= *Bulimus angosturensis* Gruner, 1841; *Bulimus hyaloideus* Pfeiffer, 1854; *Bulimus constrictus tateanus* Guppy, 1875]*Alterorhinus ovulum* (Reeve, 1849)*Alterorhinus rochai* (Baker, 1914)*Alterorhinus suturalis* (Baker, 1914)*Alterorhinus taipuensis* (Baker, 1914)**Family Bulimulidae Tryon, 1867****Unassigned subfamily****Genus *Auris* Spix, 1827***Auris bernardii* (Pfeiffer, 1856)*Auris bilabiata* (Broderip & Sowerby, 1829) [= *Helix maximiliana* "Férussac"; *Helix maximiliana melanostoma* Moricand, 1836]*Auris brachyplax* Pilsbry, 1896*Auris chrysostoma* (Moricand, 1836) [= *Bulimus melanostomus scalaris* Dohrn, 1883]*Auris egregia* (Jay, 1836) [= *Helix maximiliana minor* Moricand, 1836]*Auris illheocola* (Moricand, 1836)*Auris inornata* Simone & Amaral, 2021*Auris melanostoma* (Swainson, 1820) [= *Bulimus swainsoni* Pfeiffer, 1845]*Auris melastoma* (Swainson, 1820) [= *Bulimus listeri* Wood, 1828; *Bulimus melanostomus* Deshayes, 1832; *Bulimus rhodospirus* Potiez & Michaud, 1835; *Helix rhodospira vulgaris* Moricand, 1836; *Bulimus struthiolabris* Menke, 1830]*Auris nigrilabris* Pilsbry, 1896**Genus *Anctus* Martens, 1860***Anctus angostomus* (Wagner, 1827) [= *Stenostoma capueira* Spix, 1827; *Bulimus virgatus* Spix, 1827]*Anctus laminiferus* (Ancey, 1888) [= *Anctus pilsbryi* Ford, 1890]*Anctus prolatus* Simone & Casati, 2013**Genus *Cochlorina* Jan, 1830***Cochlorina aurisleporis* (Bruguière, 1792) [= *Bulimus lagotis* Menke, 1828; *Auricola leporis* Lamarck, 1822; *Stenostoma auritum* Spix, 1827]

Cochlorina aurismuris (Moricand, 1838) [= *Otostomus myotis* Beck, 1837; *Helix uniangulata* "Férussac" Pfeiffer, 1841]

Cochlorina intensior (Pilsbry, 1898)

Cochlorina involuta (Martens, 1867)

Cochlorina lateralis (Menke, 1828) [= *Bulimulus lyonetianus* Kuster, 1841]

Cochlorina lateritia (Pilsbry, 1898)

Cochlorina navicula (Wagner, 1827) [= *Navicula fasciata* Spix, 1827]

Cochlorina uranops (Pilsbry, 1898)

Genus *Otostomus* Beck, 1837

Otostomus signatus (Spix, 1827) [= *Auris vittata* Wagner, 1827]

Genus *Oxychona* Mörch, 1852

Oxychona bifasciata (Burrow, 1815) [= *Helix blanchetiana* Moricand, 1833; *Helicigona pyramidella spixiana* Moricand, 1836; *Drymaeus (Oxychona) bifasciatus minarum* Ancey, 1901]

Oxychona currani Bartsch, 1916

Oxychona gyrina (Deshayes, 1850)

Oxychona lonchostoma (Menke, 1828) [= *Helix bos-ciana* Férussac, 1832]

Oxychona maculata Salvador & Cavallari, 2013

Oxychona michelinae Porto, Rocha Filho, Johnsson & Neves, 2016

Oxychona pyramidella (Spix, 1827) [= *Helicigona pyramidella bipunctata* Moricand, 1836; *Helicigona pyramidella immaculata* Moricand, 1836; *Helicigona pyramidella rosea* Moricand, 1836; *Helicigona pyramidella rosea immaculata* Moricand, 1836; *Helicigona pyramidella versicolor* Moricand, 1836]

Genus *Sanniostracus* Salvador, Silva & Cavallari, 2023

Sanniostracus carnavalescus (Simone & Salvador, 2016)

Sanniostracus obliquus (Reeve, 1849) comb. nov. [= *Bulimus jeffreysi* Pfeiffer, 1852; *Drymaeus obliquus monozona* Ancey, 1901]

Sanniostracus poecilogramma (Ancey, 1901) comb. nov.

Genus *Stapafurdus* Simone, 2021

Stapafurdus costiferus Simone, 2021

Stapafurdus glaber Simone, 2021

Subfamily *Bulimulinae* Tryon, 1867

Genus *Bulimulus* Leach, 1814

Bulimulus albus (Sowerby, 1839)

Bulimulus angustus Weyrauch, 1966

Bulimulus bonariensis (Rafinesque, 1833) [= *Helix sporadica* d'Orbigny, 1835; *Bulimus montevidensis* Pfeiffer, 1846; *Bulimulus gelidus* Reeve, 1849; *Bulimulus (Drymaeus) morenoi* Preston, 1907;

Bulimulus saltensis Holmberg, 1909; *Bulimulus (Bulimulus) sporadicus schadei* Schlesch, 1935]

Bulimulus brunoi (Ihering, 1917)

Bulimulus corumbaensis Pilsbry, 1897 [= *Bulimus amoenus* Bonnet, 1864]

Bulimulus eganus (Pfeiffer, 1853)

Bulimulus erectus (Reeve, 1849)

Bulimulus fraterculus (Potiez & Michaud, 1838) [= *Bulimus diaphanus* Pfeiffer, 1855; *Bulimulus hoelmontensis* Mazé, 1883]

Bulimulus marcidus (Pfeiffer, 1853)

Bulimulus pliculosus Ancey, 1901 nomen inquirendum

Bulimulus stilbe Pilsbry, 1901

Bulimulus sula Simone & Amaral, 2018

Bulimulus tenuissimus (Férussac, 1832)

Bulimulus transparens (Reeve, 1849)

Bulimulus turritellatus (Beck, 1838) [= *Helix turritella* d'Orbigny 1835]

Bulimulus versicolor (De Cristofori & Jan, 1832)

Bulimulus vesicalis (Pfeiffer, 1853) [= *Bulimus faysianus* Saussaye, 1853]

Genus *Naesiotus* Albers, 1850

Naesiotus arnaldoi (Lanzieri & Rezende, 1971)

Naesiotus carlucioi (Rezende & Lanzieri, 1963)

Naesiotus cutisculptus (Ancey, 1901)

Naesiotus lopesi (Rezende & Lanzieri, 1972)

Naesiotus montivagus (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Bulimulus montivagus chacoensis* Ancey, 1897]

Naesiotus pachys (Pilsbry, 1897)

Genus *Protoglyptus* Pilsbry, 1897

Protoglyptus dejectus (Fulton, 1907)

Protoglyptus heterogramma (Moricand, 1836)

Protoglyptus longiseta (Moricand, 1846)

Subfamily *Peltellinae* Gray, 1855

Genus *Drymaeus* Albers, 1850

Drymaeus acervatus (Pfeiffer, 1857)

Drymaeus acuminatus Da Costa, 1906

Drymaeus bivittatus (Sowerby, 1833)

Drymaeus branneri Baker, 1914

Drymaeus bucia (Pfeiffer, 1859)

Drymaeus castilhensis Simone & Amaral, 2018

Drymaeus coarctatus (Pfeiffer, 1845) [= *Kora iracema* Simone, 2015; *Kora terrea* Simone, 2015]

Drymaeus currais Simone, Belz & Gernet, 2020

Drymaeus cuticula (Pfeiffer, 1855)

Drymaeus dakryodes Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2015

"*Drymaeus*" *expansus* (Pfeiffer, 1848) [= *Drymaeus vanattai* Pilsbry, 1898; *Drymaeus expansus bal-*

- boa* Pilsbry, 1926; *Mesembrinus expansus orcesi* Weyrauch, 1958; *Drymaeus rehderi* Parodiz, 1963]
- Drymaeus flexilabris* (Pfeiffer, 1853)
- Drymaeus germaini* (Ancey, 1892)
- Drymaeus goianensis* Dutra-Clarke & Souza, 1991
- Drymaeus henselii* (Martens, 1868)
- Drymaeus hyltoni* Parodiz, 1957 [= *Drymaeus alabastrinus* Hylton Scott, 1952]
- Drymaeus iheringi* (Leme, 1968)
- Drymaeus limicolarioides* Haas, 1936
- Drymaeus linostoma* (d'Orbigny, 1835)
- Drymaeus magus* (Wagner, 1827) [= *Bulimus inflatus* Spix, 1827]
- Drymaeus micropyrus* Simone & Amaral, 2018
- Drymaeus muelleggeri* Jaeckel, 1927
- Drymaeus nigrogularis* (Dohrn, 1882)
- Drymaeus palliolum* (Férussac, 1821)
- Drymaeus papyraceus* (Mawe, 1823) [= *Bulimus lita* d'Orbigny, 1838; *Bulimulus papyraceus latior* Strebel, 1882; *Drymaeus papyraceus var. papyrifactus* Pilsbry, 1898]
- Drymaeus paucipunctus* (Pilsbry, 1898)
- Drymaeus poecilus* (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Bulimus poecilus var. major* d'Orbigny, 1837; *Bulimus poecilus var. minor* d'Orbigny, 1837; *Bulimus pictus* Bonnet, 1864; *Bulimulus poecilus var. icterica* Ancey, 1892; *Drymaeus poecilus santanensis* Dall, 1912; *Drymaeus lynchi* Parodiz, 1946; *Drymaeus poecilus tricinctus* Parodiz, 1963]
- Drymaeus polygramma* (Moricand, 1836)
- Drymaeus protractus* (Pfeiffer, 1855)
- Drymaeus riberoi* Ihering, 1915
- Drymaeus saccatus* (Pfeiffer, 1855)
- ‡*Drymaeus schadei* Quintana & Magaldi, 1985
- Drymaeus semistriatus* Haas, 1955
- Drymaeus serratus* Pfeiffer, 1855
- Drymaeus similaris* (Moricand, 1856)
- Drymaeus siolii* Haas, 1952
- Drymaeus souzalopesi* Weyrauch, 1965
- Drymaeus subsimilaris* Pilsbry, 1898
- Drymaeus succineus* Pilsbry, 1901
- Drymaeus suprapunctatus* Baker, 1914
- Genus Antidrymaeus Germain, 1907**
- Antidrymaeus gereti* (Ancey, 1901)
- Genus Aposcutalus Dutra & Leme, 1985**
- Aposcutalus atlanticus* (Dutra & Leme, 1985)
- Genus Mesembrinus Albers, 1850**
- Mesembrinus dutaillyi* (Pfeiffer, 1857)
- Mesembrinus interpunctus* (Martens, 1887)
- Mesembrinus lusorius* (Pfeiffer, 1854)
- ‡*Mesembrinus nigrofasciatus* Pfeiffer, 1846 [= *Drymaeus nigrofasciatus elongatulus* Pilsbry, 1898]
- Mesembrinus oreades* (d'Orbigny, 1835)
- Mesembrinus puellaris* (Reeve, 1850)
- ‡*Mesembrinus roseatus* (Reeve, 1850)
- Mesembrinus rufolineatus* (Drouët, 1859) [= *Drymaeus interruptofasciatus* Vernhout, 1914; *Drymaeus chevallieri* Breure, 1976]
- Genus Pseudoxychona Pilsbry, 1930**
- Pseudoxychona dulcis* (Ihering, 1812)
- Pseudoxychona faerie* (Salvador & Cavallari, 2014)
- Pseudoxychona pileiformis* (Moricand, 1836)
- Pseudoxychona polytricha* (Ihering, 1912)
- Pseudoxychona spiritualis* (Ihering, 1912)
- Family Cycloodontinidae Salvador & Breure, 2023**
- Genus Bahiensis Jousseume, 1877**
- Bahiensis albofilosus* (Dohrn, 1883)
- Bahiensis bahiensis* (Moricand, 1834) [= *Odontostomus bahicola* Mörch, 1852]
- Bahiensis ciaranus* (Dohrn, 1882)
- Bahiensis guarani* (d'Orbigny, 1835)
- Bahiensis janeirensis* (Sowerby, 1838)
- Bahiensis longulus* (Pfeiffer, 1859)
- Bahiensis miliolus* (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Bulimus fuscagula* d'Orbigny, 1837; *Odontostomus juvenicus* Mörch, 1852]
- Bahiensis neglectus* (Pfeiffer, 1847)
- Bahiensis oblitus* (Reeve, 1848)
- Bahiensis occultus* (Reeve, 1849)
- Bahiensis reevei* (Deshayes, 1851)
- Bahiensis rhodinostomus* (d'Orbigny, 1835)
- Bahiensis ribeirensis* Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2016
- Bahiensis ringens* (Dunker, 1847)
- Genus Burringtonia Parodiz, 1944**
- Burringtonia exesa* (Spix, 1827) [= *Pupa ringens* Jay, 1836; *Helix* (*Cochlodina*) *exesa zonata* Moricand, 1841]
- Burringtonia labrosa* (Menke, 1828)
- Burringtonia leucotrema* (Beck, 1837) [= *Helix* (*Cochlodina*) *pantragruelina minor* Moricand, 1837]
- Burringtonia pantagruelina* (Moricand, 1833) [= *Helix* (*Cochlodina*) *pantagruelina major dentata* Moricand, 1837; *Helix* (*Cochlodina*) *pantagruelina major edentula* Moricand, 1837]
- Genus Clessinia Doering, 1875**
- ‡*Clessinia charpentieri* (Pfeiffer, 1850)
- Clessinia coltrorum* Simone, 2012

- Clessinia costata* (Pfeiffer, 1849)
Clessinia hilairii (Pfeiffer, 1845)
Clessinia paraguayana (Ancey, 1892)
Clessinia striata (Spix, 1827) [= *Helix spixii* d'Orbigny, 1835; *Helix spixii major* d'Orbigny, 1835; *Helix spixii minor* d'Orbigny, 1835; *Pupa conspersa* Potiez & Michaud, 1838; *Pupa turrita* Anton, 1839; *Bulimus wagneri* Pfeiffer, 1842; *Odontostomus striatus bolshi* Martens, 1894; *Odontostomus bergi* Boettger & Rolle, 1908; *Odontostomus* (*Euodontostomus*) *saltensis* Holmberg, 1912]
Clessinia uniplicata (Férussac, 1827) comb. nov.
- Genus *Cyclodontina* Beck, 1837**
Cyclodontina branneri (Dall, 1909)
Cyclodontina capivara Simone & Casati, 2013
Cyclodontina chaseae (Marshall, 1926)
Cyclodontina corderoi Klappenbach, 1958
Cyclodontina costulata (Ancey, 1904)
Cyclodontina cylindrica (Baker, 1914)
Cyclodontina fasciata (Potiez & Michaud, 1838)
Cyclodontina fusiformis (Menke, 1828) [= *Bulimus vermiculatus* Menke in Pfeiffer, 1849; *Bulimus catharinae* Pfeiffer, 1857]
Cyclodontina gemellata (Ancey in Pilsbry, 1901)
Cyclodontina iheringi (Marshall, 1926)
Cyclodontina incrassata (Ancey, 1904)
Cyclodontina inflata (Wagner, 1827) [= *Helix* (*Cochlodonta*) *brasiliensis* Férussac, 1821; *Helix* (*Cochlodonta*) *listeri* Férussac, 1821; *Clausilia pupoides* Spix, 1827]
Cyclodontina maranguapensis (Baker, 1914)
Cyclodontina punctatissima (Lesson, 1830) [= *Bulinus dentatus* King, 1832; *Auricula fuscagula* Lea, 1834; *Pupa septemplex* Mühlfeld in Rossmässler, 1837]
Cyclodontina salobrensis Solem, 1956
Cyclodontina scabrella (Dohrn, 1882)
Cyclodontina sectilabris (Pfeiffer, 1850)
Cyclodontina sexdentata (Spix, 1827)
Cyclodontina squarrosa (Ancey, 1904)
Cyclodontina tapuia Salvador & Simone, 2014
Cyclodontina trahyrae (Jaekel, 1950)
Cyclodontina tudiculata (Martens, 1868)
- Genus *Moricandia* Pilsbry & Vanatta, 1898**
Moricandia angulata (Wagner, 1827) [= *Stenostoma puru* Spix, 1827; *Plekocheilus paru* Beck, 1837]
Moricandia auriscervina (Férussac, 1821)
Moricandia bouvieri (Dautzenberg, 1897) [= *Bulimulus* (*Goniostomus*) *bouvieri alba* Dautzenberg, 1897]
Moricandia fusiformis (Rang, 1831) [= *Bulimus dubiosus* Jay, 1839]
Moricandia nasuta (Martens, 1885)
Moricandia parallela (Pfeiffer, 1857)
Moricandia tolerata (Fulton, 1903)
Moricandia willi (Dohrn, 1883)
- Genus *Plagiodontes* Doering, 1876**
‡ *Plagiodontes daedaleus* (Deshayes, 1821) [= *Odontostomus* (*Plagiodontes*) *daedaleus major* Doering, 1877; *Odontostomus* (*Plagiodontes*) *daedaleus salinicola* Doering, 1877; *Odontostomus* (*Plagiodontes*) *daedaleus minor* Pilsbry, 1901; *Odontostomus* (*Plagiodontes*) *daedaleus multidentatus* Pilsbry, 1901; *Odontostomus* (*Plagiodontes*) *weyenberghii minor* Parodiz, 1939; *Plagiodontes daedaleus costatus* Hylton Scott, 1952]
- Family “*Megaspiridae*” Pilsbry, 1904**
Genus *Callionepion* Pilsbry & Vanatta, 1899
Callionepion iheringi Pilsbry & Vanatta, 1899
- Genus *Kora* Simone, 2012**
Kora arnaldoi Pena, 2024
Kora corallina Simone, 2012
Kora nigra Simone, 2015
Kora rupestris Salvador & Simone, 2016
- Genus *Megaspira* Lea, 1836**
Megaspira adenticulata Daniel, Ovando & Santos, 2022
Megaspira elata (Gould, 1847)
Megaspira elatior (Spix, 1827) [= *Megaspira ruschenbergiana* Lea, 1836]
Megaspira gracilis Pilsbry, 1904
Megaspira iheringi Pilsbry, 1925
Megaspira pilsbryi Rehder, 1945
Megaspira robusta Pilsbry, 1904
- Genus *Thaumastus* Martens, 1860**
Thaumastus achilles (Pfeiffer, 1853)
Thaumastus ascendens (Pfeiffer, 1853)
Thaumastus baixoguanduensis Pena, Coelho & Salgado, 1996
Thaumastus caetensis Pena, Salgado & Coelho, 2011
Thaumastus contortuplicatus (Reeve, 1850)
Thaumastus dukinfieldi (Melvill, 1900) *nomen inquirendum*
Thaumastus hebes Strebel, 1910
Thaumastus largillierti (Philippi, 1845) [= *Bulimus consimilis* Reeve, 1848]
Thaumastus lundi Pena, Salgado & Coelho, 2005
Thaumastus magnificus (Grateloup, 1840)
Thaumastus nehringi (Martens, 1889)

Thaumastus parvus Pena, Salgado & Coelho, 2011
Thaumastus requieni (Pfeiffer, 1853)
Thaumastus spixii (Wagner, 1827) [= *Bulimus fragilis* Spix, 1827; *Bulimus hyalinus* Wagner, 1827; *Columna bulimea* Spix, 1827]
Thaumastus straubei Colley, 2012
Thaumastus taunaisii (Férussac, 1822) [= *Bulimus monozonalis* Deshayes, 1851]
Thaumastus tiradentensis Pena, Coelho & Salgado, 1996

Family Orthalicidae Martens, 1860

Genus *Corona* Albers, 1850

Corona duckei Ihering, 1915
Corona incisa (Hupé, 1857) [= *Corona incisa machadoensis* Strebel, 1909; *Corona machadoensis* Strebel, 1909]
Corona loroisiana (Hupé, 1857)
Corona perversa (Swainson, 1821) [= *Orthalicus reginaeformis* Strebel, 1909]
Corona regalis (Hupé, 1857)
Corona regina (Bowdich, 1822) [= *Achatina melastoma* Swainson, 1823; *Achatina melanostoma* Spix, 1827]
Corona ribeiroi Ihering, 1915

Genus *Orthalicus* H. Beck, 1837

Orthalicus bensoni (Reeve, 1849) [= *Orthalicus isabellinus* Martens, 1873]
Orthalicus capax (Pilsbry, 1930)
Orthalicus mars Pfeiffer, 1861
Orthalicus phlogerus (d'Orbigny, 1835)
Orthalicus prototypus Pilsbry, 1899
Orthalicus pulchellus (Spix, 1827)
Orthalicus undatus (Bruguière, 1789) [= *Zebra selectus* Strebel, 1909; *Zebra zoniferus naesiotes* Strebel, 1909]
Orthalicus varius (Martens, 1873)
Orthalicus zonatus (Strebel, 1909)

Genus *Sultana* Shuttleworth, 1856

Sultana meobambensis (Pfeiffer, 1855) [= *Orthalicus meobambensis carnea* Strebel, 1909]
Sultana sultana (Dillwyn, 1817) [= *Orthalicus trullisatus* Shuttleworth, 1856; *Orthalicus sultana angustior* Preston, 1914]

Family Simpulopsidae Schileyko, 1999

Genus *Leiostracus* Albers, 1850

Leiostracus cinnamomeolineatus (Moricand, 1841) [= *Bulimus lineatus* Spix, 1827]
Leiostracus clouei (Pfeiffer, 1856) [= *Bulimus fidaensis* Moricand, 1858]

Leiostracus coxeiranus (Moricand, 1836) [= *Bulimus coxiranus* Potiez & Michaud, 1838]
Leiostracus demerarensis (Pfeiffer, 1861)
Leiostracus fetidus Salvador & Cavallari, 2014
Leiostracus goniotropis (Ancey, 1904)
Leiostracus manoelii (Moricand, 1841)
Leiostracus melanosclops (Dohrn, 1882)
Leiostracus omphalodes (Menke, 1846)
Leiostracus onager (Beck, 1837) [= *Bulimus zebra* Spix, 1827]
Leiostracus perlucidus (Spix, 1827) [= *Bulimus vitreus* Spix, 1827; *Bulinus opalinus* Sowerby, 1832; *Helix angulosa* Moricand, 1836]
Leiostracus sarcochilus (Pfeiffer, 1857)
Leiostracus subtuzonatus (Pilsbry, 1899) [= *Bulimus onager* Reeve, 1848]
Leiostracus vimineus (Moricand, 1833)
Leiostracus vittatus (Spix, 1827) [= *Helix trizona* Moricand, 1836; *Helix dizona* Moricand, 1836; *Helix nigrescens* Moricand, 1836; *Helix purpurascens* Moricand, 1836; *Helix unicolor* Moricand, 1836]

Genus *Lopesianus* Weyrauch, 1958

Lopesianus crenulatus Weyrauch, 1958

Genus *Rhinus* Martens, 1860

Rhinus botocodus Simone & Salvador, 2016
Rhinus ciliatus (Gould, 1846)
Rhinus durus (Spix, 1827)
Rhinus evelinae Leme, 1986
Rhinus felipponei (Ihering, 1928)
Rhinus gilbertus Simone & Casati, 2013
Rhinus heterotrichus (Moricand, 1836) [= *Bulimulus (Rhinus) heterotrichus subtenuis* Pilsbry, 1897]
Rhinus koseritzi (Clessin, 1888)
Rhinus obeliscus Haas, 1936
Rhinus pubescens (Moricand, 1846)
Rhinus scobinatus (Wood, 1828)
Rhinus thomei (Weyrauch, 1967)
Rhinus velutinohispidus (Moricand, 1836)

Genus *Simpulopsis* Beck, 1837

Simpulopsis araujoii Breure, 1975
Simpulopsis atrovirens (Moricand, 1836)
Simpulopsis boissieri (Moricand, 1846)
Simpulopsis brasiliensis (Moricand, 1836)
Simpulopsis citrinovitreus (Moricand, 1836) [= *Bulimus vitrinoides* Reeve, 1848]
Simpulopsis decussata Pfeiffer, 1856
Simpulopsis ephippium (Ancey, 1904)
Simpulopsis eudioptus (Ihering, 1897) [= *Bulimulus (Scansicochlea) jörgenseni* Holmberg, 1912]

Simpulopsis gomesae Silva & Thomé, 2006
Simpulopsis luteolus (Ancey, 1901)
Simpulopsis miersi Pfeiffer, 1857
Simpulopsis ovata (Sowerby I, 1820) [= *Succinea obtusa* Sowerby I, 1822]
Simpulopsis progastor (d'Orbigny, 1835)
Simpulopsis promatensis Silva & Thomé, 2006
Simpulopsis pseudosuccinea (Moricand, 1836) [= *Succinea moricandi* Pfeiffer, 1842]
Simpulopsis pseudosulculosa Breure, 1975
Simpulopsis rufovirens (Moricand, 1846) [= *Vitrina salomonina* Pfeiffer, 1853; *Simpulopsis rufescens* Adams & Adams, 1855; *Simpulopsis corrugata* Guppy, 1866]
Simpulopsis sulculosa (Férussac, 1821) [= *Simpulopsis membranacea* Villa & Villa, 1841]
Simpulopsis tryoni Pilsbry, 1899
Simpulopsis wiebesi Breure, 1975

Family Tomogeridae Jousseume, 1877

Genus *Anostoma* Fischer von Waldheim, 1807

Anostoma baileyi Solem, 1956
Anostoma brunneum Verdcourt, 1992
Anostoma depressum Lamarck, 1822 [= *Anostoma verreauxianum* Hupé, 1857]
Anostoma deshaysianum Fisher, 1857
Anostoma luetzelburgi Weber, 1925
Anostoma octodentatum Fisher von Waldheim, 1807
Anostoma ringens (Linnaeus, 1758) [= *Anostoma hexodon* Fischer von Waldheim, 1807; *Angystoma resupinata* Schumacher, 1817; *Helix* (*Helicodonta*) *ringicula* Férrussac, 1821; *Anostoma globulosa* Lamarck, 1822]
Anostoma rossi Weber, 1925
Anostoma tessa Simone, 2012

Genus *Biotocus* Salgado & Leme, 1990

Biotocus cumingii (Pfeiffer, 1849)
Biotocus turbinatus (Pfeiffer, 1845) [= *Helix tomigeroi-des* Moricand, 1846]
Biotocus ubajarensis (Leme, 1980)

Genus *Clinispira* Simone & Casati, 2013

Clinispira insolita Simone & Casati, 2013

Genus *Hyperaulax* Pilsbry, 1897

Hyperaulax ramagei (Smith, 1890) [= *Bonnanius bouvieri* Jousseume, 1900; *Bonnanius bonnanius* Jousseume, 1900]
Hyperaulax ridleyi (Smith, 1890)

Genus *Tomigerus* Spix, 1827

Tomigerus clausus Spix, 1827 [= *Helix tomigera* Moricand, 1836; *Anostoma spixii* Beck, 1837; *Scarabus*

clausus Reeve, 1842]

Tomigerus corrugatus Ihering, 1905
Tomigerus esamianus Salgado & Coelho, 1990
Tomigerus gibberulus (Burrow, 1815) [= *Tomigerus principalis* Sowerby I, 1849]
Tomigerus laevis Ihering, 1905
Tomigerus matthewsi Salgado & Leme, 1991
Tomigerus pilsbryi Baker, 1914
Tomigerus rochai Ihering, 1905

Superfamily Pupilloidea Turton, 1831

Family Gastrocoptidae Pilsbry, 1918

Genus *Gastrocopta* Wollaston, 1878

Gastrocopta barbadensis (Pfeiffer, 1853) [= *Pupa auriformis* Guppy, 1868; *Pupa uvulifera* Guppy, 1868]
Gastrocopta iheringi (Suter, 1900)
Gastrocopta oblonga (Pfeiffer, 1852)
♦ *Gastrocopta pellucida hordeacella* (Pilsbry, 1890) [= *Bifidaria hordeacella parvidens* Sterki, 1899]
Gastrocopta servilis (Gould, 1843) [= *Pupa lyonsiana* Ancey, 1892; *Gastrocopta lyonsiana kailuana* Pilsbry, 1917; *Pupa microsoma* Canefri, 1883; *Vertigo shimochii* Kuroda & Amano, 1960]
Gastrocopta sharae Salvador, Cavallari & Simone, 2017
Gastrocopta solitaria (Smith, 1890)

Family Strobilopsidae Wenz, 1915

Genus *Strobilops* Pilsbry, 1893

Strobilops brasilianus Baker, 1914

Family Valloniidae Morse, 1864

Genus *Pupisoma* Stoliczka, 1873

Pupisoma dioscoricola (Adams, 1845) [= *Helix orcula* Benson, 1850; *Helix punctum* Morelet, 1851; *Helix caeca* Guppy, 1868; *Pupisoma philippicum* Möllendorff, 1888; *Pupisoma dioscoricola insigne* Pilsbry, 1920]
Pupisoma macneilli (Clapp, 1918) [= *Pupisoma minus* Pilsbry, 1920]

Genus *Vallonia* Risso, 1826

♦ *Vallonia pulchella* (Müller, 1774)

Family Vertiginidae Fitzinger, 1833

Subfamily Nesopupinae Steenberg, 1925

Genus *Bothriopupa* Pilsbry, 1898

Bothriopupa breviconus Pilsbry, 1917

Subfamily Vertigininae Fitzinger, 1833

Genus *Vertigo* Müller, 1773

Vertigo eyriesii (Drouët, 1859) [= *Bifidaria rhoadsi* Pilsbry, 1899]

◆ *Vertigo ovata* Say, 1822

Superfamily Clausilioidea Gray, 1855

Family Clausiliidae Gray, 1855

Subfamily Peruiiinae Nordsieck, 2005

Genus *Columbinia* Poliński, 1924

Columbinia orbigny (Ancey, 1892)

Genus *Pilsbrylia* Hylton Scott, 1952

Pilsbrylia dalli Simone, 2018

Superfamily Arionoidea Gray, 1840

Family Philomycidae Gray, 1847

Genus *Meghimatium* van Hasselt, 1823

◆ *Meghimatium pictum* (Stoliczka, 1873)

Superfamily Limacoidea Batsch, 1789

Family Agriolimacidae Wagner, 1935

Genus *Deroceras* Rafinesque, 1820

◆ *Deroceras agreste* (Linnaeus, 1758)

◆ *Deroceras invadens* Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011

◆ *Deroceras laeve* (Müller, 1774)

◆ *Deroceras reticulatum* (Müller, 1774)

Family Limacidae Batsch, 1789

Genus *Ambigolimax* Pollonera, 1887

◆ *Ambigolimax valentianus* (Férussac, 1821)

Genus *Limacus* Lehmann, 1864

◆ *Limacus flavus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Genus *Limax* Linnaeus, 1758

◆ *Limax maximus* Linnaeus, 1758

Superfamily Gastrodontoidea Tryon, 1866

Family Gastrodontidae Tryon, 1866

Genus *Zonitoides* Lehmann, 1864

◆ *Zonitoides arboreus* (Say, 1817)

◆ *Zonitoides nitidus* (Müller, 1774)

Family Oxychilidae Hesse, 1927 (1879)

Genus *Oxychilus* Fitzinger, 1833

◆ *Oxychilus cellarius* (Müller, 1774)

Superfamily Parmacelloidea Fischer, 1856 (1855)

Family Milacidae Ellis, 1926

Genus *Milax* Gray, 1855

◆ *Milax gagates* (Draparnaud, 1801)

Superfamily Trochomorpoidea Mörch, 1864

Family Euconulidae Baker, 1928

Genus *Euconulus* Reinhardt, 1883

Euconulus martinezi (Hidalgo, 1869)

Genus *Habroconus* Crosse & Fischer, 1872

Habroconus goyazensis (Ancey, 1901)

Habroconus mayi (Baker, 1913)

Habroconus semenlini (Moricand, 1846)

Superfamily Helicarionoidea Bourguignat, 1877

Family Ariophantidae Godwin-Austen, 1888

Genus *Tanychlamys* Benson, 1834

◆ *Tanychlamys indica* Godwin-Austen, 1883

Family Helicarionidae Bourguignat, 1877

Genus *Ovachlamys* Habe, 1946

◆ *Ovachlamys fulgens* (Gude, 1900)

Superfamily Oleacinoidea Adams & Adams, 1855

Family Spiraxidae H. B. Baker, 1939

Genus *Euglandina* Crosse & Fischer, 1870

Euglandina irakita Jardim, Abbate & Simone, 2013

Euglandina striata (Müller, 1774) [= *Achatina dactylus* Broderip, 1832; *Euglandina striatula* Vernhout, 1914; *Euglandina surinamensis* Vernhout, 1914]

Superfamily Sagdoidea Pilsbry, 1895

Family Solaropsidae Nordsieck, 1986

Subfamily Solaropsinae Nordsieck, 1986

Genus *Solaropsis* Beck, 1837

Solaropsis alcobacensis Salvador & Simone, 2015

Solaropsis amazonica (Reeve, 1854)

Solaropsis anguicula (Hupé, 1853)

Solaropsis bachi Ihering, 1900

Solaropsis brasiliiana (Deshayes, 1832)

Solaropsis caperata Silva & Mendes-Júnior & Simone 2022

Solaropsis cearana (Baker, 1914)

Solaropsis derbyi (Ihering, 1900)

Solaropsis elaps Dohrn, 1882

Solaropsis fairchildi Bequaert & Clench, 1938

Solaropsis feisthameli (Hupé, 1853)

Solaropsis heliaca (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Solaropsis paravicinii* Ancey, 1897]

Solaropsis johnsoni Pilsbry, 1933

Solaropsis juruana (Ihering, 1905) [= *Solaropsis monile peruviana* Haas, 1951]

Solaropsis leopoldina (Strubel, 1895)

Solaropsis nimbus (Simone, 2010)

Solaropsis pascalia (Cailliaud, 1857)

Solaropsis penthesileae Salvador, 2021

Solaropsis pilsbryi Ihering, 1900

Solaropsis planior (Pilsbry, 1890)

- Solaropsis rosarium* (Pfeiffer, 1850)
Solaropsis rugifera Dhorn, 1882
Solaropsis serpens (Spix, 1827) [= *Helix punctata* Wagner, 1827]
Solaropsis trigonostoma Haas, 1934
Solaropsis undata ([Lightfoot], 1786) [= *Helix* (*Solaropsis*) *pellisserpentis* Gmelin, 1791; *Planorbis pellisanguinea* Röding, 1798; *Helix colubrina* Perry, 1811; *Helix pellisserpentis minor* Moricand, 1836; *Solaropsis anomala* Pilsbry, 1957]
Solaropsis vipera (Pfeiffer, 1859)

Superfamily Helicoidea Rafinesque, 1815

Family Camaenidae Pilsbry, 1895

Genus *Bradybaena* Beck, 1837

- ◆ *Bradybaena similaris* (Férussac, 1821)

Family Epiphragmophoridae Hoffmann, 1928

Genus *Epiphragmophora* Doering, 1875

- Epiphragmophora bernardius* Ihering, 1900
Epiphragmophora semiclausa (Martens, 1868)

Genus *Minaselates* Cuezco & Pena, 2017

- Minaselates paradoxa* Cuezco & Pena, 2017

Family Helicidae Rafinesque, 1815

Genus *Cornu* Born, 1778

- ◆ *Cornu aspersum* (Müller, 1774)

Genus *Helix* Linnaeus, 1758

- ◆◆ *Helix lucorum* Linnaeus, 1758
 ◆◆ *Helix pomatia* Linnaeus, 1758

Family Labyrinthidae Borerro, Sei, Robinson & Rosenberg, 2017

Genus *Labyrinthus* Beck, 1837

- Labyrinthus diminutus* Gude, 1903 [= *Pleurodonte dacostiana* Preston, 1907]
Labyrinthus ellipsostomus (Pfeiffer, 1854) [= *Helix yatesii* Pfeiffer, 1855]
Labyrinthus raimondii (Philippi, 1867) [= *Pleurodonte fragilis* Haas, 1949]

Family Thysanophoridae Pilsbry, 1926

Genus *Lyroconus* Baker, 1927

- Lyroconus plagiopycha* (Shuttleworth, 1854) [= *Helix ierensis* Guppy, 1868]

DISCUSSION

In the present study, we recorded a total of 748 species recorded in Brazil (including three species known only as Holocene subfossils), 33 of which are exotic. This number

represents an increase from the circa 700 native species previously reported by Salvador (2019) and the total of 734 species in the TCBF Mollusca Group's report (Machado *et al.* 2023). That increase is due to new species described since and first reports of both native and exotic species. Reassessment of synonymies has also contributed to the new total, sometimes increasing but often decreasing the total number of recognized species.

Notably, since the last focused faunal catalogue (Simone 2006), there have been various discoveries, including the description of new species, redescription of a few species, and general changes in the classification of these animals. Subtle changes include reclassification of genera and species, as well as synonymizations, but a handful of broader changes also took place. (1) Firstly, several families have been recorded as native to Brazil for the first time, including Bothriembryontidae, Cystopeltidae, Vertiginidae, Thysanophoridae, and Urocoptidae. All were known from elsewhere in the Americas, except for the Cystopeltidae, which was previously restricted to Australia. The report of the first two families comes from new classification schemes based on phylogenetic studies that reallocated already-known species and genera (Salvador *et al.* 2020a, 2023a). The latter three families represent the discovery in Brazil of either species known from elsewhere in South America (Salvador *et al.* 2018b, 2021a) or new species (Simone 2022). Notably, the Urocoptidae was previously known only as fossils in Brazil (Salvador & Simone 2013; see Appendix). (2) Phylogenetic studies also allowed for some families to be “resurrected” from the literature, including Epiphragmophoridae, Simpulopsidae, Solaropsidae (now classified in Sagdoidea), and Tomogeridae (Breure & Romero 2012; Sei *et al.* 2017; Calcutt *et al.* 2020; Salvador *et al.* 2023a). Other families such as “Charopidae” and “Megaspiridae”, however, are in flux, as recent studies point out that they are non-monophyletic (Breure & Romero 2012; Salvador *et al.* 2020a, 2023a); still, their usage is retained for stability. (3) A few family-level taxa have been reclassified in an impactful manner for the taxonomy of Brazilian (and South American in general) terrestrial gastropods. The Odontostomidae were moved to Rhytidioidea (Salvador *et al.* 2023a) and the Subulinidae were split into separate subfamilies within Achatinidae (Fontanilla *et al.* 2017). Those results, however, still need further corroboration by analyses, including a broader sampling of taxa. (4) A new family, Cyclodontinidae, was described to include part of the taxa orphaned by the reclassification of Odontostomidae (Salvador *et al.* 2023a). (5) An influx of newly found exotic species has been noted, potentially powered by intensification of global trade and environmental changes

(Darrigran *et al.* 2020). Two species of note are the Japanese jumping snail *Ovachlamys fulgens* and the horntail snail *Tanychlamys indica*, which were introduced to Brazil in the past decade and have since spread rapidly throughout the country (Rosa *et al.* 2022a, 2022b).

While the most speciose families (Fig. 1) are not entirely surprising, they still point towards a better understanding of families with larger-bodied animals and an incomplete record of families containing microsnailed taxa that are extremely speciose elsewhere (e.g., Punctoidea, Gastrocoptidae), as already pointed out by previous studies (Salvador 2019; Machado *et al.* 2023). The most speciose genera (Fig. 3) include wastebasket taxa such as *Drymaeus* and *Simpulopsis*, which need a better phylogenetic framework to properly delimit different genera (e.g., Salvador *et al.* 2023). The speciose genus *Helicina* is a curious case, as Richling (2004) mentioned that the Brazilian *Helicina* spp. likely do not belong in it, and a thorough revision would allow allocation to a different genus (or genera). Other speciose genera such as *Megalobulimus* and *Streptaxis*, while seemingly cohesive on the surface, would also benefit from revisionary studies.

The reviews by Salvador (2019) and Machado *et al.* (2023) signalled some biases in the study of terrestrial gastropods in Brazil, including a collection bias against microgastropods (already mentioned above); a regional bias, with some areas of the country, notably the Midwest and the North, being less studied than others; a habitat bias, in which environments with expected high endemism (e.g., caves, altitude ecosystems) are not yet well surveyed; and the lack of attention paid to exotic species (with the notable exception of *Achatina fulica*). The malacological community in Brazil has already started to tackle some of those problems, with new studies in the Amazon (e.g., Barbosa *et al.* 2021; Lima *et al.* 2021), a better understanding of cave-dwelling species (e.g., Salvador *et al.* 2022), surveys in urban areas (e.g., Alexandre *et al.* 2017; Rangel *et al.* 2021), and more focused studies on exotic species other than *A. fulica* (e.g., Rosa *et al.* 2022b).

Most exotic species of terrestrial gastropods in Brazil were likely introduced through trade (Cowie & Robinson 2003; Darrigran *et al.* 2020), and some of the less studied ones have the potential to become agricultural pests (e.g., *Diplosolenodes occidentalis*, *Ovachlamys fulgens*, and *Tanychlamys indica*; Ramos *et al.* 2021) or act as intermediate hosts of parasites (e.g., nematodes; Thiengo *et al.* 2022). In the past years in Brazil, there have been notable advances in studying topics of significance to public health and agriculture, involving both native and exotic species of land snails and slugs (e.g., Barbosa *et al.* 2024; Rangel *et al.* 2024).

Another notable advance is that the community science platform iNaturalist is increasingly used in Brazil (Rosa *et al.* 2022a), and its numerous records can be successfully tapped to aid in biodiversity research, particularly in speciose and often insufficiently studied taxa such as invertebrates (Hochmair *et al.* 2020; Rosa *et al.* 2022a). This not only grants researchers more information on the geographic distribution of native species but also allows for the discovery of meaningful new records (and potential new species) and the tracking of exotic species' movements, provided that the such records are properly checked and vetted before any analyses are done (Rosa *et al.* 2022a; López-Guillén *et al.* 2024). Finally, iNaturalist also increases public engagement with science, enabling the community at large to contribute to (and even participate in) biodiversity research in an engaging and fun way (Brockelsby *et al.* in press).

There are still few genetic sequences available for terrestrial gastropods in Brazil apart from some phylogenetic studies and a few other publications. While DNA sequencing has become cheaper and more accessible, the reality in Global South countries, Brazil included, still prevents large-scale initiatives. The country would benefit from a DNA barcode library of its land-snail and slug species and populations, and achieving this goal should be possible in the coming decade. Similarly, obtaining genomic data of select species would be highly desirable, although for now that remains a more distant goal.

Those issues should be at the forefront of malacological studies in Brazil going forward and a broader interconnectivity of institutions and researchers in the country and abroad should not only facilitate that but also improve the scope of the research.

CONCLUSION

There is some urgency in describing and understanding the terrestrial gastropod fauna, as they (along with their freshwater cousins) have the highest extinction rates of all animal groups (Lydeard *et al.* 2004; Régnier *et al.* 2009, 2015). These animals are essential for the functioning of ecosystems, providing services as recyclers, decomposers, prey, and even predators (Barker 2001; Cameron 2016; Ovando *et al.* 2019), and their eventual demise is poised to bring cascading effects to ecosystems. Knowing and understanding our fauna is the necessary first step in protecting it. While taxonomic studies are the most urgent in that regard, particularly considering the current mass extinction we face (Wheeler 2023), further research in areas such as ecology and physiology would also be extremely advantageous, as

very little is known about the basic biology of these animals in Brazil and the roles they have in our ecosystems. Likewise, continuous efforts are necessary to understand exotic species and their surveillance and/or control.

We expect that the present checklist will serve as a tool for scientists and stakeholders in both research and conservation. We also hope that it will serve as a springboard, garnering more interest in this fauna and enabling a new wave of studies.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization: RBS. Data curation: RBS, FSS, MSM, FMM. Investigation: all authors. Visualization: CDCO. Writing (original draft): RBS, FSS, MSM, CDCO. Writing (review & editing): all authors. Supervision: RBS.

Author contributions by taxon (alphabetical order).

Achatinidae: RBS. Amphibulimidae: DCC. Bothriembryontidae: ACAS, CDCO. Bulimulidae: ALP, RBS, RMR. Charopidae: RBS. Clausiliidae: RBS. Cyclodontinidae: FSS, RBS. Cystopeltidae: RBS. Diplommatinidae: RBS. Epiphragmophoridae: RBS. Euconulidae: XMCO. Ferussaciidae: RBS. Gastrocoptidae: MSM. Helicinidae: RBS, SBS. Labyrinthidae: RBS. Megalomastomatidae: RBS. Megaspiridae: MSP, SBS, XMCO. Neocyclotidae: RBS. Orthalicidae: RBS, RMR. Proserpinidae: RBS. Scolodontidae: RBS. Simpulopsidae: ACAS, CDCO. Solaropsidae: FSS, RBS. Spiraxidae: RBS. Streptaxidae: RBS. Strobilopsidae: RBS. Strophocheilidae: FSS, MSM. Succineidae: JOA. Tomogeridae: MSM. Thysanophoridae: RBS. Urocoptidae: RBS, LRLS. Valloniidae: RBS. Veronicellidae: SRG. Vertiginidae: RBS. Exotic species: JOA, RBS, SRG. Fossils: RBS.

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APPENDIX I

CHECKLIST OF THE FOSSIL TERRESTRIAL GASTROPODS OF BRAZIL

Below a list of fossil species (pre-Holocene) is provided, according largely to the compilation of Salvador *et al.* (2018a), with some modification made by Salvador *et al.* (2023). Fossils that have been identified only to family or genus level in the literature (e.g., Maury 1934; Salvador *et al.* 2018a) were not included in the list below. The Pleistocene fossils reported by Lima & Oliveira (1992) were not included, as all species were misidentified by those authors (the low resolution of the illustrations provided

do not allow identification and the material could not be found).

Furthermore, as pointed out by Salvador *et al.* (2023), Paleogene fossils that are currently assigned to modern genera should be revised in light of the new phylogenetic framework.

Some of the fossils listed below have been considered to be conspecific with modern animals; those instances are indicated by a circle symbol (●). A double dagger symbol

(‡) is used to indicate an extinct genus.

The time period from which each fossil has been recorded is also provided in the checklist, included within curly brackets (e.g., {Miocene}). The full reference for the original description of each species is given in Appendix 2.

SUBCLASS HETEROBRANCHIA

Superorder Eupulmonata

Order Stylommatophora

Suborder Achatinina

Superfamily Achatinoidea Swainson, 1840

Family Achatinidae Swainson, 1840

Subfamily Stenogyrinae Fischer & Crosse, 1877

Genus *Neobeliscus* Pilsbry, 1896

- *Neobeliscus calcareus* (Born, 1780) {Miocene}

Genus *Stenogyra* Shuttleworth, 1854

- *Stenogyra misera* [d'Orbigny?] [uncertain taxon] {Pleistocene}

Family Ferussaciidae Bourguignat, 1883

Genus *Cecilioides* Férussac, 1814

- *Cecilioides sommeri* (Ferreira & Coelho, 1971) {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Superfamily Streptaxoidea Gray, 1860

Family Streptaxidae Gray, 1860

Subfamily Streptaxinae Gray, 1860

Genus *Streptaxis* Gray, 1837

- *Streptaxis alminoaffonsicum* (Maury, 1934) {Pleistocene}
- *Streptaxis andradai* (Roxo, 1940) {Pleistocene–Holocene}

Suborder Scolodontina

Superfamily Scolodontoidea Baker, 1925

Family Scolodontidae Baker, 1925

Unassigned subfamily

Genus *Polygyratia* Gray, 1847

- *Polygyratia polygyrata* (Born, 1778) [= *Helix elongata* Röding, 1798; *Polygyratia charybdis* Mörch, 1852] {Pleistocene}

Suborder Helicina

Superfamily Punctoidea Morse, 1864

Family “Charopidae” Hutton, 1884

Genus *Austrodiscus* Parodiz, 1957

- *Austrodiscus lopesi* Ferreira & Coelho, 1989 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Superfamily Urocoptoidea Pilsbry, 1898 (1868)

Family Cerionidae Pilsbry, 1901

‡ **Genus *Brasilennea* Maury, 1935**

- *Brasilennea arethusae* Maury, 1935 [= *Strobilops mauryae* Ferreira & Coelho, 1971] {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}
- *Brasilennea guttula* Salvador & Simone, 2012 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}
- *Brasilennea minor* Trindade, 1956 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Family Urocoptidae Pilsbry, 1898 (1868)

Genus *Brachypodella* Beck, 1837

- “*Brachypodella*” *britoi* Ferreira & Coelho, 1971 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Superfamily “Rhytidoidea” Pilsbry, 1893 *sensu lato*

Family Strophocheilidae Pilsbry, 1902

Unassigned subfamily

‡ **Genus *Eoborus* Klappenbach & Olazarri, 1970**

- *Eoborus fusiforme* Salvador & Simone, 2013 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}
- *Eoborus rotundus* Salvador & Simone, 2012 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}
- *Eoborus sanctijosephi* (Maury, 1935) [= *Carinifex fluminensis* Brito, 1967] {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Subfamily Megalobuliminae Leme, 1973

Genus *Megalobulimus* Miller, 1878

- *Megalobulimus yporanganus* (Ihering & Pilsbry, 1901) [= *Strophocheilus ovatus iguapensis* Maury, 1935; *Megalobulimus tori* Lange de Morretes, 1937] {Pleistocene}

Superfamily Orthalicoidea Martens, 1860

Family Amphibulimidae P. Fischer, 1873

‡ **Genus *Cortana* Salvador & Simone, 2013**

- *Cortana carvalhoi* (Brito, 1967) {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Family Bulimulidae Tryon, 1867

Unassigned subfamily

‡ **Genus *Itaborahia* Maury, 1935**

- *Itaborahia lamegoi* Maury, 1935 [= *Bulimulus sommeri* Palma & Brito, 1974] {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Subfamily Bulimulinae Tryon, 1867

Genus *Bulimulus* Leach, 1814

- *Bulimulus angustus* Weyrauch, 1966 {Pleistocene}
- *Bulimulus* cf. *corumbaensis* Pilsbry, 1897 {Pleistocene}

Bulimulus fazendicus Maury, 1935 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

- *Bulimulus* cf. *tenuissimus* (d'Orbigny, 1835) {Pleistocene}

Bulimulus trindadeae Ferreira & Coelho, 1971 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Subfamily Peltellinae Gray, 1855

Genus *Drymaeus* Albers, 1850

- *Drymaeus poecilus* (d'Orbigny, 1835) [= *Bulimus poecilus* var. *major* d'Orbigny, 1837; *Bulimus poecilus* var. *minor* d'Orbigny, 1837; *Bulimus pictus* Bonnet, 1864; *Bulimus poecilus ictericus* Ancey, 1892; *Drymaeus poecilus santanensis* Dall, 1912; *Drymaeus lynchi* Parodiz, 1946; *Drymaeus poecilus tricinctus* Parodiz, 1963] {Pleistocene}

Family Cyclodontinidae Salvador & Breure, 2023

Genus *Cyclodontina* Beck, 1837

Cyclodontina coelhoi (Palma & Brito, 1974) {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Genus *Plagiodontes* Doering, 1876

- *Plagiodontes* aff. *dentatus* (Wood, 1828) {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Family “Megaspiridae” Pilsbry, 1904

Genus *Thaumastus* Martens, 1860

- *Thaumastus magnificus* (Grateloup, 1840) {Pleistocene}

Family Simpulopsidae Schileyko, 1999

Genus *Leiostracus* Albers, 1850

Leiostracus ferreirai (Palma & Brito, 1974) {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Genus *Rhinus* Martens, 1860

- *Rhinus heterotrichus* (Moricand, 1836) [= *Bulimus* (*Rhinus*) *heterotrichus subtenuis* Pilsbry, 1897] {Pleistocene}

Superfamily Pupilloidea Turton, 1831

Family Gastrocoptidae Pilsbry, 1918

Genus *Gastrocopta* Wollaston, 1878

Gastrocopta itaboraiensis Salvador & Simone, 2013 {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Gastrocopta mezzalirai (Ferreira & Coelho, 1971) {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

Superfamily Clausilioidea Gray, 1855

Family Clausiliidae Gray, 1855

Subfamily Peruiiinae Nordsieck, 2005

Genus *Temesa* Adams & Adams, 1855

“*Temesa*” *magalhaesi* (Trindade, 1953) {Early Eocene: Itaboraian}

APPENDIX 2

BIBLIOGRAPHY OF ORIGINAL DESCRIPTIONS OF SPECIES-LEVEL TAXA

Below are listed all the studies containing the original descriptions of all species-level taxa in the present checklist.

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